

EVALUATION OF SITE QUALITY AND MODELLING TREE PRODUCTIVITY BY LIDAR TECHNOLOGY IN SALT-AFFECTED OAK FOREST TERRITORY

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Abstract

Forest site quality evaluation is an important part of forest planning and forest management. A forest site is characterized by forest biomass, which is determined by elevation characteristics, soil type and climate. Height of tree is widely used parameter for terroir typifying, but measuring of tree height is sometimes time- and labour-consuming and could be affected by errors. Airborne LiDAR technology is an effective tool for determining fast and accurately the tree height on a relative larger area. GIS software environment provides to prepare the high resolution digital elevation model (DEM) and digital surface model (DSM) for pixel-based canopy height. Traditionally, the operational tree height estimation can significantly differ from the actual tree heights. In our investigation, between the LiDAR-based elevation parcel map and operational tree height estimation, a close correlation ($r=0.7935$) was detected. The aim of our research was creating a site qualification map, based on airborne LiDAR data. Tree height map was completed with soil type data. Trees of different ages on the plot area, so age-based standardization was carried out by modified Chapman-Richards growth function to examine the increments of trees. In order to evaluate the forest site quality, a created increment map was categorized. Based on the results, surface hydrology features are mainly influenced by the tree increment, so the dendromass. Nevertheless, significant differences were observed between the tree increments in different soil types; higher salt content resulted in smaller (62.49%) trees in Solonetz soil.

Key words: Airborne LiDAR, remote sensing, digital surface model (DSM), digital elevation model (DEM), annual increment, Chapman-Richards growth function, agroforestry, salinization, dendromass

INTRODUCTION

Evaluation of forest site quality is one of the most important tasks for forest planning and management. Selection of the optimal tree species is a very complex part of an afforestation project. Soil analysis (Carr et al., 1991; Craigg et al., 2015), examination and evaluation of the composition and distribution of forest communities (Fekete et al., 2000), using meteorological, hydrological (Hibbert, 1976; Xu et al., 2010) and plant geography data (Cain, 1944) are essential to establish the ecological point of view of forest planning (Bettinger et al., 2008). In order to evaluate a terroir, most (laboratory and field) investigations are time- and labour-consuming. Suitable site conditions and management provide optimal stand volumes, maximal annual growth and timber volume of forest trees (Cailliez, 1980).

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Different traditional methods are available to measure tree parameters, which can help to evaluate the forest sites. Indicators, like trunk and crown diameter, tree height, stand basal area and stand volumes, tree ring analysis are such parameters, which proved information about forest grow dynamics and these parameters are responses to site conditions (Leal et al., 2017). Tree height (related with age) is one of the most informative value in a forest to evaluate of forest sites. Direct estimation of site index is based on height and age measurements from free-growing, uninjured, dominant, or dominant and codominant trees (Carmean, 1975). To determine the individual tree heights (above 6 m) by conventional methods is sometimes more difficult than younger (smaller) trees (Reid, Stephen, 1999). Nevertheless, measurement accuracy is influenced by the limits of field instruments, so incorrect conclusions can be drawn (Abed, Stephens, 2003; West, 2009).

Nowadays, remote sensing technologies and GIS software provides to survey a forest site rapidly, more accurate on relatively large area, compared to the field measurement. LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) technology is an effective tool for acquiring structural information about the trees, and about those surroundings (White et al., 2013; Maltamo et al., 2014; Hyypä et al., 2008; Næsset, 2003; Csiha et al., 2017; Riczu et al., 2016; Tamás et al., 2014; Tamás, et al., 2014) by a laser beam. Gathering forest resource information, or create forest inventory, both terrestrial laser scanning (TLS) and airborne laser scanning (ALS) are applied (Ma et al., 2017; Tamás et al., 2011). TLS systems are capable for obtaining millimeter-level (almost leaf-level), high density 3D data about the tree (van Leeuwen, Nieuwenhuis, 2010; Calders, 2015; Liang et al., 2016), but ALS can measure larger area per unit time, in lower, sub-meter 3D spatial resolution than TLS. Due to the shorter measurement ranges of TLS, large forest sites cannot be surveyed time-efficient (Bremer, Sass, 2012). Early experiments with laser-based 3D data collection from the earth surface was carried out in the 80s by the NASA (Krabill et al., 1980; Nelson et al., 1984). These investigations were established the basis of forestry survey by laser scanning system (estimating forest volume and biomass from the airborne canopy profiles, description the advantages and disadvantages the LiDAR data collection of leaf-on and leaf-off canopy conditions) (Nelson et al., 1984; Maclean, Krabill, 1986). The early LiDAR altimeter systems (Airborne Oceanographic LiDAR) were operated in visible range (green laser wavelength); penetrated to water, so applied in bathymetric researches (Hickman, Hogg, 1969). These AOL systems used discrete laser return ranging, so only one echo recorded by the laser detector (Harding, 2008). With the evolution of ALS systems and with the development of the technology, more information can be acquired about the forest. Airborne

laser scanning has already been adopted and accepted as a very valuable tool in forestry applications in the 1990s (Maas, 2010). Profiling Airborne Topographic Laser Altimeter System (ATLAS) and Airborne Topographic Mapper (ATM) systems were available in commercial use. Later, Scanning Lidar Imager of Canopies by Echo Recovery (SLICER) and the wide-swath mapping Laser Vegetation Imaging Sensor (LVIS) and waveform-recording and analyzing systems were spread (Harding et al., 2001; Maas, 2010). The emitted laser pulse hit the highest point of the object and the other part of the tree or bush (leaves, branches, trunks), and multiple reflections (multiple echoes) will be generated. The last echo deriving from the grass or the bare soil (Beraldin et al., 2010; Hollaus et al., 2014). Due to the waveform digitization techniques, the coniferous and deciduous canopy could be divided in different layers (Brandtberg et al., 2003; Persson et al., 2005; Qin et al., 2017). Beyond the acquired crown information (Korhonen et al., 2013), estimation the number of trees and the tree height (Unger et al., 2014), detection of individual trees (Persson et al., 2002), determine of each tree position (Valbuena, 2014), or the lying trees (dead woods) (Mücke et al., 2013 a; Mücke et al., 2013 b) are suitable by the airborne LiDAR technology. Obtaining this detailed information about the trees could be incorporated into the modern forestry systems.

Afforestation and forest management under extreme (soil and weather) conditions is sometimes a great forestry challenge. Different experiments are worldwide to evaluate the growing parameters of trees under harsh conditions. Poor soil depth is an important factor, which limiting forest growth (Zhang et al., 1996), but water scarcity (Mutke et al., 2005) and inland water (Fugère et al., 2016) in rooting depth cause growing problems in trees. Water transport is strongly influenced by salinization and sodification processes. Use of these salt-affected soils are sometimes difficult across the world. Around 3.8 million ha of saline soils are in Europe, and the area of saline and sodic soils are in the highest rate in Hungary (around 1 million ha, more than 25 % of European saline soils) (Jones et al., 2010). In the aspect of rational and optimal land use, afforestation experiments in salt-affected area were started in the 1800s in Hungary (Láng, 1870; Hóman, 1880; Prokopovics, 1881). Nevertheless, afforestation investigations were beginning at operational level from 1924 (Tóth et al., 1972).

The aim of our study to evaluate a salt-affected forest site, using LiDAR- and GIS-based tree heights. In order to evaluate forest terroir, a mathematical grow model is used to estimate tree increments. Based on the increments of trees, investigated area is classified in our experiment.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

One of the most comprehensive scientific afforestation and site evaluation experiment in salt-affected area are in Forest Research Institute, Püspökladány Experimental Station, in Hungary ($47^{\circ}20'44.06''\text{N}$; $21^{\circ}5'21.68''\text{E}$). Technological salinization investigations are carrying out more than on 400 hectares (from which 300 ha forest and 100 ha saline-sodic grass-land) area, in order to give guidelines to forest practice in extreme soil conditions (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Localization of the experimental forestry area

During these long-time experiments, terroir researches evaluation and tree growing assessment are prepared and also now preparing.

Forestry treatment map is derived from the Hungarian forestry web map service by the National Food Chain Safety Office. Based on the World Reference Base (WRB, 2014), soil properties of the investigated area can be

divided into soil types (Solonetz and Gleysol) and these subtype classes (Fig. 2).

Soil map of the plot area is derived from early afforestation planning data (Tóth, Várallyay, 2001). Categories of salt-affected areas are detailed by the Hungarian Soil Classification System (HSCS) (Tóth, Várallyay, 2001; Tóth, 2010). Spatial distribution of soil types is strongly depend on terrain characteristics, depth and quality of groundwater level (Szabolcs, 1959).

Fig. 2. Soil types of the investigated area

Using the available most modern technology in these investigations, more effective analysis can be implemented. LiDAR survey from the whole forested area was carried out at August 23, 2012 in the framework of ChangeHabitats2 international project. The aim of this project was to promote the use of new LiDAR technology for habitat mapping, biodiversity monitoring, environmental and nature conservation in NATURA 2000 habitat sites. The applied ALS system had analyzed the waveform, so full canopy structural investigation and terrain modeling were performed. The area was surveyed in 14 flight ranges, with 60.19 point/m² point density; the full point cloud contains more than 700 million 3D laser points with laser intensity (laser reflectance property) values.

In order to pre-process the LiDAR data (spatial cropping, cleaning the point cloud), GlobalMapper 15 software was used. Automatic LiDAR point cloud classification was not proper, so another software (ENVI LiDAR™)

was applied. Based on the spatial neighbourhood of points, automated surface recognition was prepared by ENVI LiDAR. Buildings, trees, power lines, power poles, DEM, DSM layers can be produced by the built-in algorithms. For the high-resolution analysis, DSM and DEM resolution were 50 cm. Subtracted the two layers, pixel-based tree elevation was calculated.

In order to evaluate the forest site quality, treatments of different plantation time were standardized by the tree age. Based on the Chapman-Richards growth function (Richards, 1959) – which is modified by Gál and Smith (Gál, Smith, 1985) – was applied the “general common denominator” for each forest stand (Equation 1). Beside the maximum yield estimation and maximum mean annual tree increment, Chapman-Richards equation provides the mean annual increment culminates, respectively.

$$y=p_1 \cdot (1-e^{p_2 \cdot t})^{p_3}$$

where,

p_1 – asymptotic value of the stand parameter (y) being modelled,

t – time in years,

p_2, p_3 – coefficients to be estimated.

The plot area was a 57.68 ha, which contains 71 separated examination plot. The average plot size is 0.81 ha. The investigated tree stands contain with common oak (*Quercus robur* L.), thus age-standardization and estimation of tree incrementing could be more effective than in the case of mixed stands. Using the equation, each forest stand plot was standardized (at an 81-year-old common oak, which was the oldest common oak stand of the experimental area) and a calculated increment layer was created for further GIS analysis. This calculated increment layer was added to laser-based real tree height in IDRISI Taiga software environment, so a potential tree height can be estimated. Bases on the differences between the estimated tree heights, forest site evaluation can be carried out.

Beside the assessment of increment by LiDAR and their relation between elevation and hydrology, the utilization of LiDAR for detecting the impact of different soil types on the increment of *Quercus robur* was also assessed by Tukey variance analysis to determine the statistical differences among increment of the two dominant soil types (Solonetz and Gleysol). There are two types of salinization in the investigated territory such as Saline soil (Solonchak) with high amount of water soluble soils and alkaline soil/sodic (Solonetz) high alkalinity and high exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP). High exchangeable sodium saturation of heavy-textured soil with large amount of expanding clay minerals results in unfavourable soil properties (alkaline pH in B-horizon, swelling/shrinking colloids, degradation of soil structure, limited infiltration and leaching conditions,

low water and nutrient storage capacity of shallow A-horizon), which limit their fertility, productivity and utility.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the surveyed LiDAR data, high resolution DEM and DSM were created in ENVI LiDAR software environment. Beside the relief map of the extreme flat forested area, accurate tree height map was created (Fig. 3), which is the main basis of the forest site evaluation. It can be observed, soil types (Fig. 2) are influenced by terrain characteristics.

Fig. 3. Tree height map (A), elevation (B), slope (C) and aspect (D) maps of the investigated area

The figure shows, significant differences in tree height in the given forest stands, which generally thank to the different plantation time (different age of trees). Age-based increment standardization provided the compatibility and comparability of each treatment, so a rasterized age-based treatment map was prepared. Increment calculated GIS layer for an 81-year-old common oak with the tree height map was combined. The standardized tree-increment map showed differences, which is not directly derived from the age of trees, so standardization was successful. This standardization is

strongly depend on soil characteristics and the hydrological features of the area, so early digitized soil type map was used to compare the results with soil characteristics. One of the main problem of soil maps is, that these maps were created with the cartography technique of the 1960s, and soil types or subtypes have sometimes regularly followed the borders of the treatments (Fig. 2).

Tree-incrementing and site evaluation were carried out by individual tree detection. Based on general and experimental parameters (tree height and canopy radius) of oak in different age, individual trees were detected by ENVI LiDAR software (Fig. 4). Different treatments and different ages of forest parcels on different soil type can result different growing features. Thus, automated tree identification can difficult and sometimes time-consuming. Thus, 30 m maximal tree height and 100-400 cm canopy radius values were used for individual tree detection.

Fig. 4. Elevation colored laser points in the case of 20/J forest parcel (A), location of the automated tree detection (B) with the gaps (C, D) and the vertical profile of the parcel (E), along the dotted line.

Beside individual detection of trees, 2D profile of forest parcels were analyzed in Global Mapper (Fig. 4/E). Therefore tree height (and GPS position), derived from automated tree detection and DSM-DEM-based height of trees can be compared. A close correlation ($r=0.7997$) was found between heights from automated tree-segmentation and tree heights

calculated from surface-terrain model. In the case of different age of trees and in the case of different managements (forest thinning), to get the accurate parameters (height of tree and radius of canopy) for automated tree detection by ENVI LiDAR software, is sometimes very difficult.

Thus, it is more effective, if DSM/DEM layers are using for defining the pixel-based tree heights. Determination of tree heights at operational level is carrying out in the most cases by coarse estimation, which is sometimes affected by significant errors. Compared the LiDAR-based elevation parcel map with operational tree height estimation, a close correlation ($r=0.7935$) was measured, but the operational estimation was overestimated with 3.13 m, however there were parcels with almost 7 m overestimation by the forest planner specialist (Fig. 5). Nevertheless, operational height estimation was occurred at parcel level, but LiDAR point cloud provides to determine the height of individual tree.

Fig. 5. Correlation between LiDAR-based tree height and estimated tree height by parcels

Using pixel-based elevation map from the investigated area, and applied the modified Chapman-Richards growth function, an increment map was prepared. This map strongly correlates with the tree canopy height map, but the age-based non-linear growing of trees, is more emphasize appeared on the increment map. Modified Chapman-Richards equation cannot be used for too young trees, so 17-year-old 20/I and 5-year-old 20/M parcels were ignored from the increment map.

According to the pixel-based frequency of increments, experimental area was categorized into three terroir classes; “better”, “moderate” and “worse” classes were determined. Each categories was prepared based on the histogram of tree increment. Percentiles of incremented canopy height

distribution for 20 % were calculated. Lower 20 % of the increment was the “worst”, upper 20 % was the “better” category (Fig. 6).

After filtering of the gaps, it could be established, 11.19 % of the experimental area is worse, 62.43 % is moderate and 26.38 % is better site quality. Artificial gaps in forest parcels cause false results using the equation. Thus, the twenty-four gaps, which were early prepared by the foresters in the investigated area, should have been ignored. The average area of artificial gaps is 407.69 m² and the whole gap area is almost one hectare (Fig. 7).

Fig. 6. Terroir classification based on the histogram of estimated increment

Fig. 7. Terroir categories with surface runoff

Compared the calculated terroir categories with soil types, similar “pattern” can be observed, the correlation between the variables was moderate ($r=0.3615$). Moreover, between increment map and DEM, a strong negative correlation was detected ($r=-0.5502$). The ratio of terroir categories in different soil types were analyzed (Table 1).

Table 1

Terroir categories on the investigated soil types

	Solonetz	Gleysol
Area of interest (ha)	12.21	39.40
“Worse” terroir category	28.59%	7.77%
“Moderate” terroir category	68.17%	59.19%
“Better” terroir category	3.23%	33.05%

Based on the LiDAR data the effect of soil types of increment can be evaluated. According to the results of Tukey variance analysis, increments of the two soil types are statistically different ($p<0.05$). The best results were detected on Gleysol for *Quercus robur* habitat, worse increment results were obtained on Solonetz soil type. The effect of soil types to increment is statistically proven (Table 2); trees were 62.49 % higher on Gleysol soil than on Solonetz.

Table 2

The result of Tukey variance analysis

Soil type	Increment (m)
Solonetz	9.677 ^a
Gleysol	15.485 ^b

There was no significant difference between the same numeric indices.

*Based on variance analysis ($p < 0.05$).

Gleysol and Solonetz soil types were occurred in the investigated area. The average tree height was larger on Gleysol, which suggest that *Quercus robur* is moderately salt tolerant. This moderate salt tolerating of the *Quercus robur* is reflected on the salt-sensitivity of the tree (Sehmer et al., 1995; Alaoui-Sossé et al., 1998; Tóth, 2010). In that way the effect of soil types on increment can be more effectively monitored by LiDAR system.

CONCLUSIONS

Our research hypothesis was that soil type is an important factor in tree height, but examining the annual increment, the effect of runoff, so the surface hydrology is more emphasized.

Based on this study, modern technological element (GPS, GIS, RS) can partially provide opportunity to more effective forest planning and forest management. High resolution and large amounts of 3D data can be acquired by airborne LiDAR systems. LiDAR serves such structural information about the forest, which to determine by traditional method is time-consuming or sometimes unbelievable the measuring. Used modified Chapman-Richards growth function, trees (with different age) were standardized and an increment were calculated. Percentiles of incremented canopy height distribution for 20 % were calculated, and GIS-based terroir classification map was prepared.

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POSSIBLE ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS OF THERMAL WATER UTILISATION IN NORTH EAST HUNGARY

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Abstract

The reserves and exploitation of conventional, so-called fossil energy resources are limited, therefore the utilisation of renewable energy resources has been becoming more and more important.

Present study focuses on the thermal water utilisation possibilities i.e. energy content utilisation, balneological utilisation, irrigation, and the related environmental aspects in North East part of Hungary. Among the environmental effects the total dissolved solid concentration and the methane and carbon dioxide content are examined through the examples of 66 thermal water wells screened into pannonian sensu lato (s.l.) succession.

Thermal water utilisation may have many various environmental aspects: chemical impacts, gas emission, thermal effects, water quality effects noise effects, landscape change, from which methane and solids dissolved in thermal water emitted by its extraction are highlighted.

Considering that the annual thermal water extraction from reservoirs located in the Northern part of the Great Hungarian Plain the annual Total dissolved solid concentration (TDS) and methane production can be estimated as 28,207 tones and 1,671,482 m³, respectively.

It must be highlighted that by applying cascade systems, the efficiency of thermal water utilisation can be improved while environmental aspects do not increase considerably.

Key words: geothermal energy utilisation, thermal water, environmental aspects, pannonian s.l., North East Hungary

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, global energy demand has been continuously increasing due to accelerated economic development. The reserves and exploitation of conventional, so-called fossil energy resources are limited, therefore the utilisation of renewable energy resources has been becoming more and more important. According to Lund, 2007, the geothermal energy reserves in the upper 10 km of the earth's crust are approximately 3.6×10^{14} GWh. This extractable energy could theoretically supply the global energy use for approximately 2.17 million years considering the average global energy consumption rate (Lu, 2017).

Compared to other renewable energy resources, e.g. wind and solar energy, geothermal energy cannot be affected by changes in the weather and available for a long-term period without any harmful environmental effect (Hou et al., 2018).

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In this work authors reviewed the energy status of Hungary, including the amount of primer energy used in Hungary and the proportion of the consumer sectors, studied the fields which utilize or will utilize thermal water, and presented the possible environmental aspects of geothermal utilisation.

Primer energy used in Hungary (2005-2016)

In Hungary, the rate of energy dependence is really similar to the European Union's average rate, which represents 62.8 % in 2016 (Fig. 1). Domestic and imported primer energy used in Hungary in the period of 2005-2016 has average values of 473.6 PJ and 807.81 PJ, respectively.

Fig. 1. Primer energy used in Hungary (based on data published by Hungarian Central Statistical Office)

Renewable energy resources give 3.9 % in total energy use, which has to be increased to 13 % by 2020. The distribution of the mentioned value among different types of renewable energy resources is the following:

- 88.2 % ignition of firewood and biomass,
- 8.0 % geothermal energy,
- 2.0 % electricity production from renewable energy resources,
- 0.5 % ignition of biomass and municipal solid waste,
- 0.2 % solar energy,
- 1.1 % other (e.g. wind energy).

In Fig. 2, the main energy consumers in the period of 2005-2016 can be seen: population, transportation, agriculture and commercial and public institutes.

Total annual energy consumption of the sectors, where geothermal energy can possibly come up as an energy resource, i.e. industry (137 PJ), population (262 PJ) commercial and public places (113.8 PJ), agriculture, forestry and fishery (all together 22 PJ) is approximated as 535 PJ, based on calculating the average annual energy consumption values of the sectors in Hungary within the period between of 2005 and 2016.

Fig. 2. Average annual energy consumption (TJ) by sectors in Hungary (2005-2016) (based on data published by Hungarian Central Statistical Office)

According to the study of Zilahi-Sebess et al., 2012, the annual geothermal energy potential originating from porous media is 60 PJ while from crystallized basement 130 PJ in Hungary.

Comparing these data, it can be stated that geothermal energy can provide significant proportion of energy need of the above presented sectors of energy consumers. Accordingly, energy need of agriculture, forestry, fishery and commercial and public places, all together or a significant part of the energy need of the population, can be provided by geothermal energy.

By involving geothermal energy into the energy system of Hungary, its energy dependence can be reduced, the absolute value and proportion of the renewable energy can be increased and other added values can be generated such as job creation, developing industry, ensuring sustainability (Sabău, 2015).

Utilisation types

Geothermal energy utilisation generally involves a wider group than thermal water utilisation, since it also includes the shallow geothermal and deep geothermal utilisation, as well. This study focuses on the thermal water

and its energy content utilisation possibilities and the already existing capacities and the related environmental aspects in North East part of Hungary.

Based in data published in River Basin Management Plan 2 of Hungary the annual thermal water production rate in Hungary within the period of 2008-2013 extracted from porous reservoirs and karst thermal water was 72587 million m³ from which the proportions are 69 % and 31 %, respectively (HAS, 2017). Its utilisation structure is presented by Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Average annual amount of thermal water extracted in Hungary between 2008 and 2013, and the proportions of utilisation fields both from thermal karst and porous thermal reservoirs

According to this data, it can be stated that 69 % of the extracted thermal water was stored in porous thermal water reservoirs, half of which was utilised by spas and medical institutes, almost a quarter of it was utilised for energy production and almost another quarter of it for communal reasons. In comparison, thermal water extracted from thermal karst was utilised by spas and medical institutes in greater proportion while for energetic purposes with a lesser proportion and the other utilisation fields show similar rates.

The use of thermal water mainly depends on its temperature, secondly on its chemical composition. Utilisation field of thermal water in function of its temperature is presented by the well established Lindal-diagram. In general, it can be stated that water with temperature above 60 °C can be used for heating, domestic hot water production and industrial processes (Iancu et al., 2011), while water with temperature below 60 °C can be utilized for agricultural utilisation and balneological utilisation.

It is to be noted that water at temperatures higher than 60 °C can also be utilized in the latter two utilisation fields after cooling to the right temperature. Water with high dissolved solid content has a very good physiological effect hence favourable in balneological utilisation and this utilisation form of it is quite popular in NE Hungary. There is some greater spas for instance Hajdúszoboszló and Debrecen two of which had an

extraction amount of 2.6 million m³ in 2008 (Bódi et al., 2015), and some smaller spas for instance Hajdúböszörmény, Hajdúnánás, Hajdúdorog. The latter three spas extracted approx. 0.37 million m³ thermal water in 2008. Their wells extracting from the Pannonian porous thermal water reservoirs.

Effects of thermal water utilization on environment

Thermal water utilisation may have many various environmental aspects: chemical impacts, gas emission, thermal effects, water quality effects (both for underground and surface water), noise effects, landscape change, from which methane and solids dissolved in thermal water emitted by its extraction are highlighted (Maochang, 2001).

Methane is a greenhouse gas, therefore its emission results in unfavorable environmental effects. From the solids dissolved in the extracted thermal water the sodium, chloride and hydrogen carbonate concentrations are highlighted since thermal water in the focus area are known as sodium chloride water from deeper reservoirs and sodium chloride and carbonated water from shallower reservoirs. These dissolved salts may be deposits within the system (e.g. pipes) or the environment causing serious damages. Their treatment is needed but also costly (Ghergheș et al., 2011).

Estimation of the above mentioned effects is crucial from the aspect of sustainable and environment friendly utilisation (Sameer et al., 2013).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Hydrogeological documentation containing measurement results (e.g. dissolved solid concentration, methane, carbon dioxide, oxygen) of 66 thermal water wells located in NE part of the Great Hungarian Plain were overviewed. The following properties and values were collected: well head temperature (°C), depth of the deepest screening (m), value of sodium ion (mg/l), chloride ion (mg/l) and hydrogen carbonate ion (mg/l), total dissolved solid value (mg/l) and methane-water ratio (l/m³).

Since well head temperature defines the utilisation fields, as it is presented in Lindal diagram, wells were grouped into 5 categories based on the well head temperatures. These categories are: 30 °C-40 °C, 40 °C-50 °C, 50 °C-60 °C, 60 °C-70 °C, 70 °C-80 °C. It is assumed that the parameters depend on the depth of the reservoir we extract thermal water from, main statistical parameters of the above listed properties for each group of the wells are calculated.

The aim is to give an estimation for ordering of magnitude of both the methane and total dissolved solids extracted by thermal water annually in Hungary based on the presented data sets. It is important to note, that to give

more accurate estimations, measured extraction parameters is need for each producing thermal wells.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The total dissolved solids concentration (TDS) values of studied thermal wells in wide range: min.: 1,107.4 mg/l (Tiszacsege K108), max.: 13,304.5 mg/l (Hortobágy K11). In the case of water with lower TDS concentration both the amount and the rate of chloride ion significantly lower than in water with higher TDS concentration (Fig. 4 and Fig. 5).

It is explained by the fact that higher chloride concentration originated from marine paleoenvironment. From such reservoir higher sodium ion concentration is expected, as well. In the case of spas the typical TDS concentration value ranges between 3000 mg/l and 5000 mg/l.

According to the TDS values calculated for all groups it can be stated that water with higher temperature is likely to contain a higher amount of dissolved solids, however, over 60 °C TDS mean values are around 4,100-4,600 mg/l (Fig. 6).

Fig. 4. TDS concentration (mg/l), methane-water ratio (MWR) (l/m³) and well head temperatures (°C) (1)

Fig. 5. TDS concentration (mg/l), methane-water ratio (MWR) (l/m³) and well head temperatures (°C) (2)

Fig. 6. Mean and standard deviation values of total dissolved solids (TDS) concentration (mg/l)

The standard deviation is significant in most groups. It can be explained by hydrogeological characteristics of the reservoirs. The arithmetic mean of the TDS concentration values for all wells is 4,339.6 mg/l.

If TDS values of thermal water are studied within one well but from different depths, that means different screening depths, a significant rise in concentration can be measured. Hajdúszoboszló I is an example for that (Table 1).

Table 1

Screening depth intervalls (m)	Total dissolved solids TDS (mg/l)
1,088 – 1,094	5,572
1,284 – 1,288	1,0695.48
1,366 – 1,369	1,6231.52
1,373 – 1,376	1,6303

The mean values of methane extracted with 1 m³ thermal water show variety in a wider range, standard deviation is considerable (Fig. 7).

The lowest mean values occur in both the lowest temperature and the highest temperature group. Extremities occur in wells with well head temperature higher than 40 °C but lower than 70 °C. The arithmetic mean of the methane values for all wells is 257.2 l/m³.

Fig. 7. Mean and standard deviation values of methane (l/m³)

Considering that the annual thermal water extraction from reservoirs located in the Northern part of the Great Hungarian Plain based on 2008-2013 data series is 6,500,000 m³/year and using the TDS mean and the

average methane content the annual TDS and methane production can be estimated as 28,207 tones and 1,671,482 m³, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

High TDS content has a significant effect on the soil in case of irrigation and during water treatment processes. If salt content capture could be solved the deponisation of that amount of salts would mean a significant environmental burden and challenge, moreover, it is considered to be costly.

However, the decrease of the groundwater table of the forests of NE Hungary for instance the Great Forest in and nearby Debrecen, or the forest steppes on the sandy lands of the Nyírség is a well-established fact and from this aspect thermal water could mean an irrigation alternative if its salt content would not be so considerable. Irrigating with thermal water can affect very harmful both the biosphere and the soil, therefore it is certainly not advisable without any pre-treatment or a very firm argument.

It is important to note, that if a spa is not connected or only recently connected to the local water infrastructure system, its waste thermal water treatment practice is simply about relasing water to surface water bodies. It could have taken considerable size since balneological and recreational utilisation form of thermal water has had great importance and history in Hungary, especially in NE Hungary. Thermal water used in spas is non-rejectable it is treated with sewage and rain water and its effects on the environment strongly depend on the technology applied in the treatment plant. However, it can be clearly stated that by the intensification of this thermal water utilisation way the already occurred environmental effects will be intensified but new ones will not occur.

If thermal water is used for non-balenological purposes, therefore high TDS content is not a requirement, it is more suggested to extract from a reservoir water of which has lower salt content accepting the fact that its temperature may be lower that is around 50 °C hence the energy which can be produced from it lower as well. This is mainly regarding to the energy production utilisation ways. For irrigation purposes that water is considered to be high-temperated but due to lower TDS content it can be prosperous.

Methane content is considered high in cases of several wells, relative to the extracted water. Its capturement and then its combustion by gas motor in order to produce electricity is favorable. By combustion other greenhouse gases such as water vapor and carbon dioxide are emitted which is unfavorable therefore this emission must be reduced, as well.

It must be highlighted that by applying cascade systems, the efficiency of thermal water utilisation can be improved while environmental aspects do not increase considerably.

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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC QUANTIFICATION OF GREEN PIGMENTS AND TOTAL CAROTENOIDS FROM MISTLETOE GROWN ON DIFFERENT HOST TREES

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Abstract

Mistletoe (Viscum album subsp. album) is native from Europe and is a hemiparasitic plant that lives on different host trees. This plant depends for water and mineral nutrition on its host trees, but is able to have own photosynthesis to produce organic substances.

The main objective was to quantify the chlorophyll a and b, and total carotenoids from leaves of mistletoe that are grown up on four different host trees (apricot, sallow, hawthorn and sweetbrier) in two different periods (December, 2017 and April, 2018). The mistletoe samples have been harvested on December (2017) and April (2018) from the North-East of Romania near Mişca, Bihor county. The photosynthetic pigments were measured by spectrophotometric method using ethanol as solvent.

The differences between the levels of green pigments from leaves of mistletoe growing of different host trees and different seasons were noticed. Leaves of mistletoe harvested on winter showed the highest content in photosynthetic pigments compared with leaves harvested on spring. The composition and contents of photosynthetic pigments appear to be important for the determination of physiological characteristics of Viscum album subsp. album growing of different host trees.

Key words: *Viscum album subsp. album*, chlorophylls, *Prunus armeniaca*, *Salix L.*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Rosa canina*

INTRODUCTION

V. album L. is a medicinal plants used in the traditional medicine and in complementary cancer therapies (Stan et al., 2013).

The genus *Viscum* has been placed in its own family *Viscaceae*, but recent genetic research by APG III system shows this family to be correctly with in family *Santalaceae* (Bössing, 2000). *Viscum album subsp. album* is a hemiparasitic plant that depends for water and mineral nutrition on its host trees. It contains all green pigments: chlorophyll *a* and *b* as well as carotenoids that are necessary for photosynthesis (Vicas et al., 2010).

The chlorophylls of higher plants consist of chlorophyll *a* as the major pigment and chlorophyll *b* as accessory pigments.

Traditional methods for analysis of photosynthetic pigments employed spectroscopy and extinction coefficients that had been calculated for a range of solvents. To extract chlorophyll pigments from plant tissue, several solvents were used. For example, acetone, N,Ndimethylformamide,

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methanol, ethanol, dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) have been used for analysis of photosynthetic pigments (Porra et al., 1986; Ayari et al., 2000; Porra et al., 2002; Krause et al., 2003; Manetas et al., 2003; Newsham, 2003; Berveiller et al., 2007; Ritchie, 2008; Vicas et al., 2010; Pallag et al., 2016).

The aim of our work was to compare the levels of photosynthetic pigments (chlorophyll *a*, chlorophyll *b* and carotenoids) from leaves of mistletoe (*Viscum album* subsp. *album*) growing on four different host trees (apricot, sallow, hawthorn and sweetbrier) in two different periods (December, 2017 and April, 2018).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Site description and plant material

This study was conducted in December of 2017 and April of 2018 on the North-East of Romania near Mișca locality, located at an altitude of 198 m, at the sea level, with the following coordinates: 47°26' north and 22°26' east, therefore, in the north-east of Bihor County ([http://ro.getamap.net/harti/romania/bihor_misca.](http://ro.getamap.net/harti/romania/bihor_misca)). Average temperature: -10°C (winter) and +30°C (summer). Winters are not too long or severe and summers are thermally moderate. The frequent air mass is oriented eastward. Precipitation varies between 400-500 mm / year, with periods of drought. The soils in the area are Haplic Luvisols (Sabău, 2017).

The host trees from which the mistletoe leaves are harvested are in the semi-shaded and sunny area.

The leaves of mistletoe have been harvested from four host species: apricot (*Prunus armeniaca*), willow (*Salix vitellina*), hawthorn (*Crataegus monogyna*) and brier (*Rosa canina*) in two different periods: winter and spring. Leaves sample were collected in the field, immediately placed in plastic bags, and stored to -22°C, until assayed.

Quantification of plants green pigments and total carotene using ethanol solvent

For extraction of chlorophyll *a* and *b*, 50 mg leaves were mixed with 5 ml ethanol 70 % (v/v) using Ultra Turrax homogenizers (SilentCrusher M instruments, Heidolph). After 24 and 48 hours, the samples were centrifuged at 12000 rpm, for 10 minutes, at 4°C. The supernatants were separated and the levels of green pigments were determined by using a mini UV-VIS Shimadzu spectrophotometer.

The absorbances obtained after spectrophotometric determination were mathematically processed (Porra, 2002), using the formulas presented in the Table 1 (Sumanta et al., 2014). The results were expressed as µg chlorophyll/ml and µg total carotenoids/ml.

The mistletoe was harvested from four host trees and they were labelled according with the host trees, thus: VA_A (apricot-*Prunus armeniaca*), VA_W (willow-*Salix alba*), VA_H (hawthorn-*Crataegus monogyna*) and VA_B (brier-*Rosa canina*) for easy identification. Full-sun exposed young leaves of mistletoe from horizontal branches of host trees were used for analysis.

Table 1

Equations for the determination of Chlorophyll *a* [Chl *a*] and *b* [Chl *b*] concentrations and total carotenoids ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) (Sumanta et al., 2014)

Solvent	Equations for chlorophyll concentrations ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) determination
Ethanol	$[\text{Chl } a] = 13.36\text{Abs}^{664} - 5.19 \text{Abs}^{649}$ $[\text{Chl } b] = 27.43\text{Abs}^{649} - 8.12\text{Abs}^{664}$ $\text{Total carotenoids} = 1000 \text{Abs}^{470} - 2.13 \times [\text{Chl } a] - 97.63 \times [\text{Chl } b] / 209$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Fig. 1 is shown the levels of chlorophyll *a*, chlorophyll *b* and total carotenoids ($\mu\text{g/ml}$ ethanolic extract) from leaves of *Viscum album* subsp. *album* that are growing on apricot trees (VA_A). For the quantification of photosynthetic pigments we used both spring (Fig. 1A) and winter (Fig. 1B) leaves at two different extraction time (24 and 48 hours).

Fig. 1. The levels of chlorophyll *a*, chlorophyll *b* and total carotenoids ($\mu\text{g/ml}$ ethanolic extract) from leaves of *Viscum album* subsp. *album* that are growing on apricot trees (VA-A). A. Ethanolic mistletoe extract, prepared from leaves harvested on spring (April 2018) using two different time of extraction, 24 and 48 hours, respectively. B. Ethanolic mistletoe extract prepared from leaves harvested on winter (December 2017) using two different time of extraction, 24 and 48 hours, respectively

Before the analyses, the leaves of mistletoe were stored at -22°C . The freezing process leads to the formation of ice crystals that can broke the cell

wall, and thus the cellular content may be released (Chassagne – Berces et al., 2009).

Leaves of mistletoe harvested on winter showed the highest content in photosynthetic pigments compared with leaves harvested on spring. In the spring mistletoe leaves samples, the highest extraction time (48 hours) did not lead to a higher pigments extraction. In contrast, the highest extraction time (48 hours) in the winter leaves samples did lead to a higher pigments content (Fig. 1B and Fig. 2).

In Fig. 2 is shown the absorbance spectrum (from 400 to 900 nm) of ethanol mistletoe leaves extract, at two different time of extraction (24 and 48 hours respectively).

Fig. 2. The comparative absorbance spectrum from 400 to 900 nm of ethanol mistletoe leaves extracts (harvested on December 2017) depending on the extraction time, 24 and 48 h respectively

The maximum absorbance for chlorophyll was 3.999 at 446 nm and 3.0979 at 654 nm. Chlorophylls exhibit two major light absorption bands, one of the blue side of the visible spectrum (< 460 nm) and one in the red (630 -670 nm). The maximum absorbance for chlorophyll *a* was 666 nm and 434 nm, and for chlorophyll *b* was 653 nm and 453 nm (Vicas et al., 2009).

The content of chlorophyll *a*, *b* and total carotenoids of ethanol extract of mistletoe leaves growing on four host trees (*Prunus armeniaca*, *Salix alba*, *Crataegus monogyna* and *Rosa canina*), harvested on April and December is shown in Fig. 3A and B, respectively.

The highest content in chlorophyll *a*, chlorophyll *b* and total carotenoids was recorded in the case of winter leaves of mistletoe growing

on the apricot trees followed by mistletoe growing on willow and hawthorn. The lowest content in photosynthetic pigments was recorded in the case of mistletoe harvested from bier. Chlorophyll extraction is depending on the type of solvents and time extraction (Sumanta et al., 2014).

Ethanol as solvent play an important role in the extraction of green pigments and total carotenoids from the leaves of mistletoe. These results are similar with the study of Dunn et al., (2004). Also, the extraction time is important for the quantification of green pigments. Our results shown that the best time was obtained after 48 hours extraction.

Fig. 3. A. The content of chlorophyll *a*, *b* and total carotenoids of ethanol extract of spring mistletoe leaves samples growing on four host trees VA_A (apricot), VA_W (willow), VA_H (hawthorn) and VA_B (brier). B. The content of chlorophyll *a*, *b* and total carotenoids of ethanol extract of winter mistletoe leaves samples growing on four host trees

The high amount of chlorophyll *a* and total carotenoids are found in winter mistletoe leaves harvested from the apricot and hawthorn trees.

CONCLUSIONS

The composition and contents of photosynthetic pigment appear to be important for the determination of physiological characteristics of *Viscum album* subsp. *album* growing of different host trees.

Mistletoe leaves originating from apricot trees followed by mistletoe growing on willow showed the higher concentration of chlorophyll *a* and *b*, when the leaves were collected in the winter. The lowest content in photosynthetic pigments was recorded in the case of mistletoe harvested from bier. Leaves of mistletoe harvested on winter showed the highest content in photosynthetic pigments compared with leaves harvested on spring. The levels of photosynthetic pigments differ depending on the time of harvest and the nature of the host trees.

We assume that the host trees of mistletoe may play a significant role in the phytochemical composition, including also the photosynthetic pigments.

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CARBON, NITROGEN AND SULFUR CONTENTS AND RATIOS IN SOME HUNGARIAN SOIL TYPES

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Abstract

The residues of organic matter in the soil are transformed biologically over a shorter or longer time period. In the humification process, a part of the organic decomposition products formed the dark-coloured humus. The other part of the organic matter is also decomposed by the activities of heterotrophic organisms, in which inorganic substances are produced from the organic matter. The direction and intensity of the transformation, however, depends not only on the organic material stock of the soil but also on the organisms in the soil. They are closely related to soil properties, natural fertility, environmental factors and applied agrotechnical processes. The rate and speed of humus formation and mineralization processes determines the soil organic matter stock and the set of nutrients that can be uptaken by plants during the degradation of organic matter. The transformation of alternative plant nutrient, organic matter (composts, green manure, sewage sludge, slurry etc.) is determined by the living organisms with different activities in the soil.

In present publication the results of most important physical and chemical properties of 12 different soil types in eastern part of Hungary (chernozem, meadow, marsh, brown forest soil, blown sand, and solonetz) are analysed. The vegetation of involved soil types were: winter wheat, orchard, oak forest and natural grassland. There were also determined the total content (stock) of some main elements (C, N, S, P) in the soils and their ratios (C/N, C/S, N/S) were compared also. There were investigated the available nutrient content of the soils (CaCl₂ solution extractable nitrate and sulfate content). Based on the results, there was also calculated the proportion of the available and the total element content of soils.

Key words: carbon, nitrogen, sulfur content and ratio, available nutrient, soil types

INTRODUCTION

The inorganic nutrient forms are of primary importance for the nutrient supply of plants.

Most of the total carbon, nitrogen and sulfur content of soils are found in organic compounds. During the transformation and mineralization of organic matter, nutrients will be available for the plants. The chemical forms of carbon, nitrogen and sulfur will be modified by the transformation of soil organic matter content (Oneţ et al., 2013). The inorganic nutrient forms available to plants are of primary importance nutrient supply of plants.

The content and chemical forms of nutrient elements of various soils are considerably different. The C:N:S ratios in Hungarian soils are approximately 100:10:1, respectively (Stefanovits et al., 1999). Brady, 1990 compared the C:N:S ratios of soils were found 147:10:1.4 in Scotland,

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between 114:10:1.6 and 145:10:1.0 in North America, and between 140:10:1.5 and 152:10:1.2 in North-Eastern part of Australia.

The goals of our investigation were, to determine the plant available nitrate-N and sulfate-S content, the total CNS stocks and to calculate the C:N:S ratio in some Hungarian soil types. Furthermore, the plant available ratios of soil's total N and S content were calculated.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The most important physical (soil texture, plasticity index) and chemical properties (pH in water and KCl solution, hydrolytic acidity, CaCO₃ and salt content) of 12 different soil types (chernozem, meadow, brown forest soil, blown sand, and solonetz) in eastern part of Hungary were analysed by description of Buzás, 1988.

Vegetation of soil types were: maize, orchard, oak forest and natural grassland (Table 1).

Table 1

Location and vegetation of soil types studied (2014)

Sampling code	Soil taxonomy (World Reference Base)	Location	Vegetation
1.CCh	Chernozems	Debrecen Látókép	maize
2.MCh	Chernozems	Debrecen-Látókép	maize
3.ChM	Vertisols	Hajdúböszörmény	maize
4.TM	Vertisols	Hajdúböszörmény	maize
5.MM	Vertisols	Debrecen – Dombos tanya	grassland
6.HSf	Arenosols	Debrecen - Pallag	oak forest
7.HSo	Arenosols	Debrecen - Pallag	orchard
8.BC	Luvisols	Debrecen - Pallag	orchard
9.BR	Cambisols	Pocsaj	grassland
10.BI	Luvisols	Pocsaj	grassland
11.MS	Solonetz	Hortobágy	grassland
12.SS	Solonetz	Pocsaj	grassland

The total C, N and S stocks were measured by using ELEMENTAR VARIO EL (Hanau, FRG) analyser. The plant available nitrate and sulfate content of soils were analysed in 0.01 M/dm³ CaCl₂ extract.

Soil samples were collected in the autumn of 2014. The laboratory measurements were made in 3 replications. The results were analysed statistically with the SPSS.13.0 program. There were calculated one-way ANOVA, and significant difference on 5 % level. The differences are signed in the tables with letters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The texture of the studied soils were: sand, loam and clays loam. Most of the analysed soils are weakly acidic and neutral, except for MM, which is strongly alkaline and BC, which is acidic. Among the soils, the hydrolytic acidity value of ChM, BC and MS indicates the need for soil amelioration. The lime content of the MM and the total soluble salt content of the MS are remarkable (Table 2).

Table 2

The most important parameters of examined soil types

Code	Texture	Plasticity according to Arany	pH H ₂ O	pH M KCl	Hidrolytic acidity (y ₁)	CaCO ₃ %	Salt %
1. CCh	Loam	46	6.13	5.45	7.85	-	0.039
2. MCh	Clayes loam	51	7.74	7.19	-	1.25	0.041
3. ChM	clay	52	6.40	5.29	11.2	-	0.022
4. TM	Clayes loam	55	6.58	5.46	7.60	-	0.025
5. MM	Clayes loam	58	9.53	8.13	-	26.7	0.022
6. HSf	Sand	38	6.79	6.02	5.07	-	0.005
7. HSo	Sand	26	7.23	6.49	-	-	0.003
8. BC	Sand	28	5.38	4.04	8.16	-	0.002
9. BR	Loam	50	7.34	6.77	-	0.21	0.028
10. BI	Clayes loam	45	7.12	6.32	-	-	0.011
11. MS	Clayes loam	54	5.92	5.11	8.19	-	0.049
12. SS	Clayes loam	48	7.60	7.27	-	1.8	0.259

Total element contents

The total carbon content of soils is the sum of organic and inorganic forms of carbon. The most of organic carbon is present in the soil's organic matter, while the inorganic carbon can be found in carbonate minerals, too. As it is well known, the 56 – 58 % of the organic matter content is organic carbon. Organic carbon in soils can be determined by the differences of total carbon and inorganic carbon contents, too (Nelson, Sommers, 1982).

According to their carbon content, the most of the soils in Hungary are generally in the medium category. On the basis of their nitrogen content they can be classified as poorly or moderately supplied category (Várallyay et al., 2006). Most of the studied soils have carbon content between 1.93 and 3.12 % (Table 3). The soils of ChM, TM and MM have higher carbon

content, and a lower level of carbon was determined in soil types of HSo, BC and SS.

Table 3

Changing of total C, N and S content and their ratios in some Hungarian soil types

Soil types	C (%)	N (%)	S (%)	C/N	C/S	N/S
1. CCh	1.93a	0.21a	0.07a	9.19a	27.57a	3.00a
2. MCh	2.24a	0.22a	0.06a	10.18a	37.33a	3.67a
3. ChM	*4.01b	0.33a	0.06a	12.15a	*66.83b	*5.50b
4. TM	*3.62b	0.30a	0.05a	12.07a	*72.40b	*6.00b
5. MM	*7.20d	*0.47c	0.05a	*15.32b	*144.00c	*9.40c
6. HSf	2.27a	0.21a	0.04a	10.81a	*56.75b	*5.25b
7. HSo	0.84a	*0.08b	0.03a	10.50a	28.00a	2.67a
8. BC	*0.34c	*0.04b	*0.02b	8.50a	17.00a	2.00a
9. BR	2.09a	0.22a	0.04a	9.50a	*52.25b	5.50a
10. BI	1.97a	0.21a	0.04a	9.38a	49.25a	5.25b
11. MS	*3.12b	0.33a	0.07a	9.45a	44.57a	4.71a
12. SS	*0.69c	*0.07b	*0.02b	9.86a	34.50a	3.50a
*LSD _{5%}	1.19	0.13	0.05	5.72	30.17	2.41

Values indicated by various letters are significantly different from each other

The total nitrogen content in the surface layer of most cultivated soils contains between 0.06 and 0.5 % (Bremner, Mulvaney, 1982; Ardelean, 2011). The organic nitrogen ratio is regularly between 97 and 99 % of total N, while the inorganic one is only a few percent. According to nitrogen contents (0.2 to 0.4 %) the most of the analysed Hungarian soil types are moderately supplied. Soil type of MM has a higher (0.47), and soil types of HSo, BC and SS have a remarkably lower (0.04 to 0.08%) total nitrogen contents.

According to Tabatabai, 1982 the organic sulfur ratio of the total one's is mostly higher than 95 %. In the well aerated soils, most of the inorganic sulfur normally occurs in form of sulfate. The total sulfur contents of mineral soils ranges between less than 20 ppm in sandy soils and larger than 600 ppm in heavy texture soils.

The average sulfur content of the Hungarian soils is 0.06 %, but it can reach the extremely high content of 2 % for solonetz, too. From 70 to 90 % of the total sulfur content of soils is found in organic compounds (Debreczeni, 1979). According to our measurements the total sulfur results changed in a narrow intervals (S % = 0.02 - 0.07).

Ratios of total element contents

The C/N ratio in arable soils ranges mostly from 8:1 to 15:1, averaging 10:1 to 12:1 (Brady, 1990). According to our measurements, the analysed soils are in this range, in most cases they are from 9:1 to 12:1.

It is well known, that in the soils the most important feature of plant residues are C:N. If this value is smaller than 80, the plant residues decompose relatively quickly. If the C:N is above 80, the decomposition process of the plant residues is a slow reaction.

It was also found in the literature, that the C:N ratio of soils is around 10:1 (Füleky, Rajkainé Véig, 1999). If the C/N ratio is higher than 30 at the initial decomposition of the soil organic matter, the nitrogen content in the soil is bound. If the C/N ratio is below 20, the mineral nitrogen is released during the mineralization process of the organic materials.

Stevenson, 1986 reported a C:S proportion of 108:1 in the soils. Similarly, Brady and Weil, 2010, found that the C:N:S ratio is 100:8:1 in stable organic matter content of soils.

According to Füleky and Rajkainé Véig, 1999, the ratio of C:N:S in soil's organic matter is around 100:10:1. If the C or N ratio is higher, the S is incorporated into the organic matter. Obviously, if the mentioned ratios are lower, the sulfur content is released during the mineralization.

Based on our results, the 100 C:S ratio varied between 0.69 and 5.88 (Table 4). It is noteworthy that larger values (CCh, MCh, HSo, BC), which exceed the literary values, were found in the agriculturally cultivated soils.

Table 4

Changes in soil use and the ratio of carbon and sulfur in soils

Soil types	C (%)	S (%)	C/S	100 C/S	sulfate S µg S/g soil	land use
1. CCh	1.93a	0.07a	27.57a	3.60	49.69	maize
2. MCh	2.24a	0.06a	37.33a	2.67	28.72	maize
3. ChM	*4.01b	0.06a	*66.83b	1.50	8.20	maize
4. TM	*3.62b	0.05a	*72.40b	1.38	7.03	maize
5. MM	*7.20c	0.05a	*144.00c	0.69	7.35	grassland
6. HSf	2.27a	0.04a	*56.75b	1.76	6.08	forest
7. HSo	0.84a	0.03a	28.00a	3.57	6.19	orchard
8. BC	*0.34c	0.02b	17.00a	5.88	6.97	orchard
9. BR	2.09a	0.04a	*52.25b	1.91	6.58	grassland
10. BI	1.97a	0.04a	49.25a	2.03	7.06	grassland
11. MS	*3.12b	0.07a	44.57a	2.10	43.16	grassland
12. SS	*0.69c	0.02b	34.50a	2.90	18.91	grassland
*LSD _{5%}	1.19	0.05	30.17	-	-	-

Values indicated by various letters are significantly different from each other

Sulfate S also showed higher values in CCh and MCh soil types as well as in MS and SS soils. Higher C/S and sulfate content may be due to regular application of sulfate-containing fertilizers, such as gypsum, containing superphosphate and/or ammonium sulfate.

In the Table 5 it can be found the proportion of plant-available nitrate nitrogen and sulfate sulfur in the ratio of total nitrogen and sulfur content of soils, respectively.

Table 5

The 0.01 M/dm³ CaCl₂ soluble nitrate and sulfate content in a ratio of total nitrogen and sulfur content of some soil types in Hungary (µg/g)

Soil types	NO ₃ ⁻ -N	Total N	NO ₃ ⁻ -N/ Total N	SO ₄ ²⁻ -S	Total S	SO ₄ ²⁻ -S/ Total S
1. CCh	4.95	2100	0.24	49.69	730	6.81
2. MCh	5.60	2200	0.25	28.72	550	5.22
3. ChM	1.29	3300	0.04	8.20	600	1.37
4. TM	1.90	3000	0.06	7.03	540	1.30
5. MM	3.44	4700	0.07	7.35	520	1.41
6. HSf	0.43	2100	0.02	6.08	400	1.52
7. HSo	0.36	800	0.05	6.19	290	2.13
8. BC	0.51	400	0.13	6.97	200	3.49
9. BR	5.96	2200	0.27	6.58	350	1.88
10. BI	0.39	2100	0.02	7.06	350	2.02
11. MS	0.48	3300	0.01	43.16	680	6.34
12. SS	0.51	700	0.07	18.91	220	8.60

It can be stated that, depending on soil properties and soil use, the soil types CCh, MCh, BC, BR have a higher content of 0.01 M/dm³ CaCl₂ soluble (plant available) nitrate content than the other soils. The soil types of ChM, TM, MM, BR also have a higher content of plant available nitrate too, but in these soils, the organic nitrogen is less mobilizable. The amount of plant available sulfate S, similar to the nitrate, is higher in CCh, MCh, BC soil types, and also, in the soils with elevated salt content.

CONCLUSIONS

It was found that the majority of the analyzed soils have an average stock of organic carbon and nitrogen. All the sulfur content of the soils has changed in a narrow interval.

According to the literature data the C:N ratio of soils changed between 8:1 and 15:1. In the examined soils the C:S proportions are from 100:0.69 to 100:5.88. Literature data are mainly close to 100:1.

The results showed that the sulfur content of investigated soils were higher than average, especially for soils under agricultural cultivation as well as for salty (meadow solonetz and solonchak-solonetz) soil types. The higher sulfur content of cultivated soils is likely due to regular application of sulfate containing fertilizers.

If the CaCl₂ soluble nitrate content reached 0.25-0.27 % of the total ones, it can be considered as outstanding. The higher sulfate-S content is

from 5 to 8 % of the total sulfur content. The CaCl₂ extractable nitrate and sulfate content showed that higher values were found in the cultivated soils, than in the other ones.

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THE INFLUENCE OF BASE TEMPERATURE ON SWEET SORGHUM PRODUCTION IN HUNGARY

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Abstract

In order to reach the goal determined by the 2009/28/EU directive sorghum production for energy purposes can be an adequate method. Efficient sorghum production is based on the consideration of the climatic aspects. An advantage of sorghum is appearing in the field of drought tolerance. The foundation of sorghum's great drought tolerance is the high heat demand which must be fulfilled.

The heat demand varies from 8 °C to 15 °C, so that based on the meteorological data recorded in the period of 1997-2016 the Effective Heat Unit varied between 627 °C and 2097 °C. Base temperature has a remarkable impact on the length of the vegetation period as well. Depending on this value the potential length of the vegetation period can vary from 123 days to 153 days. The sugar accumulation curve of a sorghum hybrid is also an important aspect of efficient bioethanol production where length of the vegetation period is an essential factor.

Key words: base temperature, heat unit, sweet sorghum, sugar accumulation, bioethanol

INTRODUCTION

The 2009/28/EU directive appropriates the increase of the rate of renewable energy up to 20% in communal energy consumption of the EU countries by 2020 in order to support the broader dissemination of renewable energy. In 2012 the share of renewable energy sources in the Central and Eastern European Countries ranged from 9.6% to 35.8% and in the case of four countries the share of renewable energy sources was below the average of EU-28 which was 14.1% (IEPP, 2014). Regarding the Central and Eastern European Countries natural gas is the main source of energy in Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania and Slovakia, while coal is a notable energy source in Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Poland and Romania in addition high energy dependency often reveals in the Region (IEEP, 2014). Agricultural lands are finite hence the competition for arable lands can be increase between the sectors of food- and energy production (Smith et al., 2010). One way to prevent food vs fuel competition is to cultivate biomass crops on marginal areas (e.g., dry environments) that are not currently being used for the production of food crops.

Sorghum species can be excellent crops for biomass energy production in the Central and Eastern European Region, especially sweet

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sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench), which is a widely used basic material for bioethanol production in the world regarding the high sugar content accumulated in the juice of the stem (Bryan, 1990; Billa et al., 1997; Dolciotti et al., 1998; Barbanti et al., 2006; Zhao et al., 2009).

Sorghum is a very prospective crop in Hungary due to its great tolerance against drought and unfavorable soil conditions, which are actual problems in the Hungarian agriculture (Nagy et al., 2014). It was an important and widely adapted crop grown between 40 °N and 40 °S of the Equator in the 20th century (Doggett, 1988). Due to the effective sorghum breeding processes and the climatic adaptation of this plant the geographical boundaries of sorghum production have been expanded in the recent decades. Hungary was formerly considered to be the northern border of sorghum production (Chrappan et al., 1997). Nowadays several publication report about the effective sorghum production from countries northern than Hungary (Idziak et al., 2013; Pazderu et al., 2014; Adamčík et al., 2016).

The general heat unit of sorghum usually varies between 2600 °C and 3300 °C (Faragó, 1975; Horváth, Mikes, 1981; Késmárki, 2005). This parameter is often in correlation with the length of the vegetation period, which varies between 90 and 300 depending on the variety, with the most frequent range being 150–200 days (Craufurd et al., 1999; FAO, 2000; Geleta, Labuschagne, 2005).

The base temperature of the grown sorghum variety is a determinative factor of the climatic adaptation. By this parameter the effective heat unit can be calculated which is the useful heat amount for the crop during vegetation period. According to Monk, 1977, Angus et al., 1981 and Gerik et al., 2003 the base temperature of sorghum is 10 °C while this parameter ranged from 8.3 °C to 12.2 °C in the report of Craufurd et al., 1999. According to Parthasaranthi et al., 2013 this value varies between 8 °C and 10 °C.

In this study the impacts of the base temperature on the potential length of vegetation period of sweet sorghum hybrids were evaluated. Based on the meteorological data of the period from 1997 to 2016 the probability of risks caused by cold temperature were determined appearing either in the beginning or in the end of the vegetation period. The optimal length of the vegetation period of sweet sorghum within the Hungarian conditions were calculated and the shape of the refractometric dry material (Rdm) content accumulation curve of six sweet sorghum hybrids were determined.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This research work was carried out in the Research Institute of Karcag in Hungary (N 47° 23', E 20° 56', Above Mean Sea Level: 87 m). Meteorological parameters were recorded with 10 minutes frequency by a

VAISALA QLC-50 automatic meteorological meter. Based on the recorded data between 1997-2016 the dates of frost appearing in late spring and early autumn were selected. The calculated dates were classified with 5 days and the occurrence frequencies were determined focused on the investigated period, so as, to determine the risks caused by the length of the vegetation period.

Effective Heat Units (EHU) were determined by Eq. 1. Calculations referring to the period from 20th of April to 10th of October. In the case of EHU values the base temperature has ranged from 8 °C to 15 °C with 0.5 °C scale.

$$EHU = i \sum_1^n \frac{(T_{i,MIN} + T_{i,MAX})}{2} - T_B; \quad \text{Eq. 1.}$$

where:

$T_{i,MIN}$: daily minimum temperature (°C)

$T_{i,MAX}$: daily maximum temperature (°C)

T_B : base temperature (°C)

n: length of vegetation period (day)

The field experiments were fixed on the plant growing sites of the Research Institute of Karcag. The soil type of the non-irrigated production areas were Haplic phaeozem (WRB). Field experiments were carried out between 25th of April and 31th of November in 2008-2016 so as, to evaluate six sweet sorghum hybrids. The average annual precipitation was 549.5 mm and annual average temperature was 11.5 °C respectively. During the sowing the applied row space was 76.2 cm, the distance of the plants was 5 cm and the depth of sowing was 5 cm as well. The plant stocks were free of weeds, pests and pathologic symptoms. As fertilizer ammonium - nitrate was used added to field before sowing with the dose of 100 kg/ha.

Refractometric dry matter content, which is in a strict correlation with sugar content (Izsáki, 2004; Liu et al., 2008; Kawahigashi et al., 2013) was determined by refractometer weekly in the period of August – November of each evaluated hybrid. Measurements were based on the juice pressed out from the internodes between the 3. and 4. nodes of the stalk. Based on the measured Refractometric dry matter contents, the shapes of the Rdm content curves were determined by polynomial regression analysis. Calculations and data management were done by MS Office Excell while statistical analyses were performed by using and R software with R Studio user service (R Core Team, 2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the meteorological data recorded in the surveyed two decades the Effective Heat Unit varied between 627 °C and 2097 °C. By

taking into consideration that sorghum varieties can be characterized with different base temperature, remarkable distinctness appear in the field of the useful amounts of heat. According to this result the value of base temperature of a sorghum variety is a determinative factor of sorghum production within Hungarian climatic conditions.

If a sorghum variety can be characterized with a base temperature of 8 °C, the average effective heat unit is about 1810 °C, while in the case of 15 °C base temperature useful heat sum is only 761°C, which is not enough to produce sorghum with a low level of climatic risks (Table 1).

Table 1

Effective Heat Unit and length of vegetation period in case of different base temperature stages

T _B	Effective Heat Unit (°C)				Length of vegetation period (days)			
	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Min	Max
8	1810	145.58	1563	2097	152.9	0.22	152	153
8.5	1735	145.19	1493	2021	152.9	0.22	152	153
9	1660	144.83	1423	1946	152.9	0.45	151	153
9.5	1584	144.45	1353	1870	152.5	0.83	150	153
10	1509	144.04	1284	1795	152.2	1.06	150	153
10.5	1434	143.5	1215	1719	151.4	1.5	148	153
11	1359	142.94	1147	1644	150.6	2.03	146	153
11.5	1285	142.19	1079	1568	149.9	2.17	146	153
12	1211	141.23	1011	1493	148.7	2.62	144	153
12.5	1139	140.1	945	1417	146.8	3.41	140	153
13	1067	138.67	879	1343	144.8	3.63	138	151
13.5	996	136.96	814	1268	142.1	4.61	131	151
14	926	134.89	751	1195	139.4	4.95	129	149
14.5	859	132.77	690	1122	136.8	5.63	126	148
15	791.81	130.47	627	1052	133.4	6.2	123	143

Base temperature has a remarkable impact on the length of the vegetation period as well. Depending on this value the potential length of the vegetation period can vary from 123 days to 153 days. By increasing the value of base temperature the standard deviation and range values of EHU are increasing as well which phenomenon reflects on the climatic risk of sorghum with high heat demand.

Sorghums are basically sown in the beginning of May and harvested in the beginning of October. This is a short period for this plant, so that a higher heat demand can be provided by choosing varieties with a lower base temperature.

If the vegetation period is longer a high risk factor is appearing due to the probability of cold temperature in the late spring or early autumn.

Regarding the evaluated two decades the latest frost in spring were observed in the period of the 10th of March and 25th of April, while 55 % of the total registered latest frost were registered in April. The late spring frost were appeared nine times (45 %) in the period from 10th of April to 25th of April hence the probability of late spring frost is the highest in these days. Considering this fact lengthening the vegetation period by sowing in an early time is not a prospective method. Frost can cause serious damage on sorghum plants, therefore a remarkable risk is appearing if the vegetation period is expanded by sowing before May (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The frequency of late spring frost (left) and early autumn frost (right) in spring (days)

Early frosts in autumn can cause serious problems as well, which is a remarkable risk factor if considering the fact that 75 % of the earliest frosts were registered in October. Thus, the extension of the vegetation period in autumn is also fraught with risk.

By the viewpoint of bioethanol production early autumn frost can be very harmful by the sugar loss caused by the chilling injury. This sugar loss can be remarkable, because sorghums usually reach the maximum amount of sugar content in the stage of waxy maturity. The sugar accumulation curve is in coherence with the length of the vegetation period, so that the shape of the accumulation curve is also typical for each hybrid. This can be a very important characteristic of a variety regarding the purposes of sugar production.

The shape of these curves were different in every cases, hence the dynamic of sugar accumulation in the stalks were different. The Rdm

accumulation curve of Hybrid 1 achieved the peak point in the mid of October, while peak point was reached of the Rdm accumulation curve of Hybrid 3 in the beginning of October (Fig. 2). In every other cases the top of the curve were hit in November. These hybrids have a longer vegetation period than 180 days, which is not fit for the Hungarian climatic conditions. In Hungary harvesting sweet sorghum in November is unfavorable, because in this case the risks of frost damage are enhanced. Thus, early maturity hybrids are acceptable for growing in Hungary.

0: aug. 0 – 9 3: szept. 0 – 9 6: okt. 0 – 9 9: nov. 0 – 9
 1: aug. 10 – 19 4: szept. 10 – 19 7: okt. 10 – 19 10: nov. 10 – 19
 2: aug. 20 – 31 5: szept. 20 – 30 8: okt. 20 – 31 11: nov. 20 – 31

Fig. 2. Rdm accumulation curves in the case of the investigated sweet sorghum hybrids

However differences in the shape of the Rdm accumulation curves can be beneficial as well. If the goal of the sweet sorghum growing is to produce sugar, the application of hybrids with different length of vegetation period can be effective so as to maximize sugar yields. Thus in the field of bioethanol production an enhanced amount of alcohol can be produced by an extended harvesting period. In this case, by dividing the production site to separated fields growing early and medium maturity hybrids an increased sugar yield can be provided.

CONCLUSIONS

According to this survey, it can be set out that sorghum can be an adequate crop to produce biomass for bioenergy purposes, considering the impacts of climate change. In this point of view, the drought tolerance of sorghum is a determinative aspect, but on the other hand the heat demand of a sorghum hybrid must be fulfilled in order to produce sorghum efficiently. The heat demand of a sorghum is depending on the base temperature of cultivated variety. Base temperature is usually varies from 8 °C to 15 °C. If the base temperature is high, the production possibilities are unfavorable due to the low heat sum, which can be useful for the plant. Thus, sorghum hybrids characterized with 10 °C or lower base temperature can be prospective within the Hungarian climatic conditions.

The length of the vegetation period is an important factor as well. Based on the meteorological data of the investigated two decades frosts can cause serious damage on sorghum lands. Spring frosts and autumn frosts can also appear during the vegetation period of sorghum, which can results serious yield and sugar loss.

In order to produce sugar from sorghum the shape of the sugar accumulation curve is an important aspect. By considering the sugar accumulation curve, sorghum based bioethanol production can be fitted to the climatic conditions, moreover by choosing adequate hybrids a longer harvesting period can be maintained with the maximum sugar amount.

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STUDIES ON PLANT GROWTH AND WINTER RESISTANCE OF SOME MANGOLD VARIETIES GROWN IN WESTERN ROMANIA

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Abstract

Mangold (Beta vulgaris ssp.cicla L.) is grown for leaf petiole, but also leaves can be consumed in different culinary dishes. Mangold (petiole beet) is grown since antiquity by all the peoples of the Mediterranean area, nowadays culture is known in most European countries, including northern areas. In Romania it is a species less known, being cultivated on small surfaces.

Experience was carried out during 2017-2018, in a vegetable farm, in locality of Săcueni, Bihor County, favorable for the cultivation of mangold due to specific pedoclimatic conditions. Seven cultivars of mangold were studied, which were cultivated in the field. Objectives were to follow plant growth, their production as well as their resistance over the winter.

The highest yield of 19.39 kg/m² was recorded at Lucullus variety, with 34.74 % above the average, followed by Verte of Carde Blanche, with over 27.03 % above the average. Mangold plants resisted over 80 % in winter.

Key words: mangold, cultivar, production, resistance to low temperatures

INTRODUCTION

Petiole beet or mangold (*Beta vulgaris* L., ssp.*vulgaris* sin.ssp.*cicla*, convar.*vulgaris*, var. *flavescens* DC.) is grown for whole leaves or only for petiole which is pleasant to taste, tender and juicy (Ciofu et al., 2004).

In Romania, a less cultivated species, is present in some areas of Transylvania (Bei et al., 2015). Being a species with lower requirements for temperature can be cultivated in all areas, except mountain areas. It has resistance to high temperatures (over 35 °C), thus a great summer vegetable for the southern areas (Lagunovschi-Luchian, Vânătoru, 2016).

It is considered a vegetable with a vital impact in healthy eating, and is therefore a vital part of a healthy diet due to the rich content of leaves in nutrients, especially vitamin A, vitamin C, vitamin E, folic acid, calcium, iron and dietary fiber. Yellow-orange, red-violet-colored mangolds are also a good source of cathenoid substances in the form of provitamin A, which the body transforms into vitamin A. It also has a high vitamin K content with a key role in blood coagulation (Rana, 2016).

Leaves and petiole contain vitamin C, carbohydrates, cellulose, protein substances, mineral salts (potassium, sodium, phosphorus, calcium).

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It is recommended in the diet of diabetes patients, it is a good digestive, has antiinfectious properties and contributes to good circulation of blood (Pokluda, Kuben, 2002).

Content of leaves in mineral elements, quantitative and qualitative production are influenced by fertilization (Santamaria et al., 1999). Shannon et al. (2000) considers mangold a vegetable with a high tolerance to soil salinity, which is why in such conditions the plants accumulate in the leaves higher amounts of sodium compared to other vegetables.

Petiole is white in most varieties but there are varieties of colored petiole in different shades of red, yellow-orange or violet, which also have a distinctive decorative aspect (Apahidean, Apahidean, 2000; Cristea, 2014).

In general, culture is set up by sowing directly into the field, in spring, second decade of April. Depending on the harvest period, sowing can take place until July 15th (Indrea et al., 2012).

However, spring crop production may be double compared to autumn culture (Kolota et al., 2010). A characteristic is the short period of vegetation, plants are ready to be harvested after 60-70 days, after crop establishment.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Experience was carried out between 2017-2018, being located in a vegetable farm, in Săcueni, Bihor county, in the western part of Romania. Climate of the area has high heliothermal values and high water resources (Pereş et al., 2016).

Average monthly multiannual temperature in the experimental area has positive values since February (0.3 °C), then reaches 5.0 °C in March, at 10.5 °C in April, in May 15.8 °C. Average annual temperature is 8-10 °C. In 2017, the precipitation value was 604.7 mm. Soil on which the experience was placed was alluvial.

Purpose of the experience was to determine how some cultivars of field mangold cultivate in the conventional crop system and their resistance to winter conditions to ensure leaf harvest in spring of the following year.

Cultivars Carde Blanche d'Ampuis, Bright Yellow, Liscia Verde da Taglio, Charlotte, Verte and Carde Blanche, Lucullus and Couleurs Rainbow were used in the experience (7 experimental variants, placed in three rehearsals).

Carde Blanche d'Ampuis is a variety that has petioles with a width of 10-12 cm, white in color. It is a rustic variety, of special quality, with leaves in a vertical position, with dark green leaves.

Bright Yellow is a variety with leaf petioles and yellow veins, with a strong contrast that ensures a great decoration. In young state it can be used in salads. It is resistant to premature flowering, can be cultivated from early

spring to late autumn. Leaves height reaches up to 50 cm and the width of the leaf up to 40 cm.

Liscia Verde da Taglio is an early variety, from which leaves are consumed as spinach. Plant has an erect port, leaves are green-glossy. Harvested after 50 days after emergence. It is adapted to cold, temperate climates.

Charlotte is a variety of red petioles with vivid, ornamental shades. Young leaves or leaf petiole can be used at full development. Also suitable for crops in containers.

Verte a Carde Blanche is a typical long-white, well-developed, petiole mangold. Leaves are dark green in color. Young plants are used in salads or preparations like spinach and the petiole is cooked or steamed, like celery petiole. In order to obtain vigorous plants, for petioles, spring cultures are recommended.

Lucullus is a kind of mangold that forms well-grown petioles of medium length, white, leaves are dark green with white veins, harvested after about 60 days after emergence, is resistant to high summer temperatures.

Couleurs Rainbow is a variety of mangold with well-developed red-orange petioles. Leaves are lightly embossed with orange red veins, which ensures an ornamental appearance of the plants. It is adapted to a warm climate, harvested after at least 45 days after emergence.

Experience was placed in the field and was established by direct sowing on 17.08.2017 on a properly prepared land (fertilized from autumn with 40 t/ha decomposed manure), after a sweet corn culture. After emergence, plants were rarefied, then the usual maintenance work was carried out. Leaves harvesting began in October and lasted until December.

Observations were made on plant growth, plant height, leaf rosette diameter, leaf length, leaf/plant number, petiole length and thickness at the base of the plant, and the percentage of plants that resisted at specific conditions during winter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Growth of mangold plants was different depending on variety. Thus, leaf rosette diameter, after 30 days after emergence, averaged 24.45 cm. Highest value of 31.88 cm was recorded at *Lucullus* variety, followed by *Verte a Carde Blanche* (29.00 cm). *Couleurs Rainbow* variety had the smallest diameter of the leaf rosette, 18.33 cm. Mangold leaves had an average length of 15.61 cm, with variations from 12.30 cm (*Charlotte*) to 19.29 cm (*Lucullus*). Leaf petiole had an average length of 4.90 cm, with values between 3.66 cm (*Charlotte*) and 5.85 cm (*Liscia Verde da Taglio*). Thickness of leaf petiole had average values of 0.44 cm with variations

between 0.32 cm and 0.60 cm. Average number of leaves per plant was 3.98, with fairly small variations, between 3.66 and 4.55 leaves/plant (Table 1).

Table 1

Variety influence on the characteristics of the mangold leaves,
30 days after emergence

Variant	Rosette leaf diameter (cm)	Leaf length (cm)	Petiole length (cm)	Petiole width (cm)	No. leaves/plant
Carde Blanche Ampuis	27.22	15.94	4.82	0.46	3.77
Bright Yellow	25.20	15.46	5.79	0.43	3.66
Liscia Verde da Taglio	20.00	15,68	5.85	0.43	4.33
Charlotte	19.55	12.30	3.66	0.33	3.88
Verte a Carde Blanche	29.00	17.06	4.76	0.52	3.66
Lucullus	31.88	19.29	4.96	0.60	4.55
Couleurs Rainbow	18,33	13,56	4,49	0,32	4,00
Average	24.45	15.61	4.90	0.44	3.98

After 60 days from emergence, autumn-grown mangold plants had a leaf rosette diameter of 31.33 cm (Couleurs Rainbow) and 66.00 cm (Verte a Carde Blanche), with an average of 52.74 cm (Table 2). Mangold leaves had between 18.46 cm (Couleurs Rainbow) and 28.98 cm (Liscia Verde da Taglio) in length. Leaf petiole was on average 8.67 cm long with variations between 6.74 cm and 12.98 cm and petiole thickness was between 0.56 cm and 2.19 cm. Average number of leaves per plant in the 7 varieties was 6.31 (between 5.00-7.33 leaves/plant).

Table 2

Variety influence on the characteristics of the mangold leaves,
60 days after emergence

Variant	Rosette leaf diameter (cm)	Leaf length (cm)	Petiole length (cm)	Petiole width (cm)	No. leaves/plant
Carde Blanche Ampuis	56.22	26.44	7.65	1.98	6.77
Bright Yellow	50.00	26.25	9.10	1.08	5.55
Liscia Verde da Taglio	57.11	28.98	12.98	0.73	7.33
Charlotte	44.00	25.15	8.04	0.75	5.77
Verte a Carde Blanche	66.00	27.99	8.74	2.19	6.77
Lucullus	64.55	28.32	7.44	1.56	7.00
Couleurs Rainbow	31.33	18.46	6.76	0.56	5.00
Average	52.74	25.94	8.67	1.30	6.31

Leaf harvesting began in October and lasted until December (Table 3). At the first harvest, yield was between 3.74 kg/m² (Charlotte) and 6.63 kg/m² (Lucullus), second harvested between 3.29 kg/m² (Charlotte) and 7.78 kg/m² (Verte a Carde Blanche) and at the third harvest leaf yield was between 2.15 kg/m² (Bright Yellow) and 5.21 kg/m² (Lucullus). Production dynamics were better for Lucullus variety, followed by Verte of Carde Blanche.

Table 3

Variant	Harvesting date			Total
	14.10.2017	18.11.2017	6.12.2017	
Carde Blanche Ampuis	5.26	5.44	3.67	14.37
Bright Yellow	4.05	3.32	2.15	9.52
Liscia Verde da Taglio	5.42	5.06	3.72	14.20
Charlotte	3.74	3.29	2.95	9.98
Verte a Carde Blanche	4.07	7.78	4.43	18.28
Lucullus	6.63	7.55	5.21	19.39
Couleurs Rainbow	5.77	5.22	4.03	15.02

Average production of autumn mangold was 14.39 kg/m² (Table 4). Maximum yield of 19.39 kg/m² was recorded at Lucullus variety, with 34.74 % above average, the production difference being very significant. Cultivar Verte a Carde Blanche recorded a production increase of 27.03 %, with the difference in production being very significant. Charlotte and Bright Yellow varieties recorded lower yields, below the average, with very significant negative differences.

Table 4

Variant	Total production kg/m ²	Relative production (%)	± diff kg/m ²	Difference Signification
Carde Blanche Ampuis	14.37	99.86	-0.02	-
Bright Yellow	9.52	66.15	-4.87	ooo
Liscia Verde da Taglio	14.20	98.67	-0.19	-
Charlotte	9.98	69.35	-4.41	ooo
Verte a Carde Blanche	18.28	127.03	3.89	xxx
Lucullus	19.39	134.74	5.00	xxx
Couleurs Rainbow	15.02	104.37	0.63	-
Average	14.39	100.00	-	-

LSD (P 5%) 1.02

LSD (P 1%) 2.56

LSD (P 0.1%) 3.78

In areas with mild winters, mangold plants can withstand winter, so it is possible to make some harvests during early spring (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Winter resistance of mangold plants (original)

Under the specific conditions of western Romania, in the winter of 2017-2018 (Table 5), in autumn crops, the percentage of plants that resisted low winter temperatures was over 50 %, with the exception of Charlotte variety (8.13 %). A good percentage of over 80 % was recorded for Liscia Verde da Taglio (86.92 %), Couleurs Rainbow (85.57 %) and Carde Blanche Ampuis (84.96 %).

Table 5

Plant resistance at low winter temperatures

Cultivar	Average no. of plants/variant		% resistant plants
	30.11.2017	15.04.2018	
Carde Blanche Ampuis	13.30	11.30	84.96
Bright Yellow	12.67	7.30	57.62
Liscia Verde da Taglio	13.00	11.30	86.92
Charlotte	12.30	1.00	8.13
Verte a Carde Blanche	14.67	11.67	79.55
Lucullus	14.67	11.67	79.55
Couleurs Rainbow	11.30	9.67	85.57

CONCLUSIONS

On the basis of the results obtained during research on field mangold, under the specific conditions of West of Romania, using cultivars Carde Blanche d'Ampuis, Bright Yellow, Liscia Verde da Taglio, Charlotte, Verte of Carde Blanche, Lucullus Couleurs Rainbow, following conclusions were drawn:

After 60 days from emergence, autumn cultivated mangold plants had a different growth. Varieties Verte a Carde Blanche, Lucullus and Liscia Verde da Taglio had higher plant growth.

Production dynamics was better for Lucullus variety, followed by Verte of Carde Blanche;

- The highest yield of 19.39 kg/m² was recorded at Lucullus variety, with 34.74 % above the average, followed by Verte of Carde Blanche, with over 27.03 % above the average.

- Mangold plants resisted over 80 % in winter, Liscia Verde da Taglio (86.92 %), Couleurs Rainbow (85.57 %) and Carde Blanche Ampuis (84.96 %).

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THE RESULT OF THE NON-COMPLIANCE ASPECTS FOR THE AIR AND WATER, IN THE OIL EXTRACTION OF SUPLACU DE BARCĂU AND THE MEASURES REQUIRED FOR THEIR PROTECTION

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Abstract

Pollution of air, water and soil in the Barcău basin is due to anthropogenic activities carried out in production units that aim to exploit oil and gas fields and crude oil processing.

Following studies on gas emissions to the atmosphere, as a result of the oil extraction activity on the S.C. PETROM S.A. Suplacu de Barcău, nonconformities were found in accordance with the Environmental Legislation, due to high concentrations of carbon monoxide – CO. The value of 7.5 mg/m³ in the oil extraction fields exceeds the maximum admissible concentration of 6 mg/m³.

The main cause of pollution of surface water is the discharge of industrial waste waters. The physico-chemical characteristics of the industrial waste waters indicates exceedances of the permissible legal limits, observed at the entrance to the treatment plant for both years of observations (2010 and 2011) at: CBO₅ 1177 - 1484 mg/l; Phenols 3.2-3.4 mg/l; The filtration residue 1968 – 1988 mg/l; The dry residue (MTS 105 °C) 611- 914 mg/l; The fixed residue (MTS 600 °C) 101 – 116 mg/l; The volatile residue (MTS volatile) 81 – 89 mg/l.

Due to the dilution recorded after the wastewater discharges treated in the Barcău River, the values of the main monitored physicochemical indicators fall within the permissible limits, being below the maximum values of STAS 4706-88, Category III rivers, except the oil products indicator, which is more than 5 times the admissible value.

The main technical and organizational measures necessary to prevent the pollution of the Barcău River are: the increasing the efficiency of the treatment plant, identifying the sources of accidental pollution, stopping discharges and removing them.

Key words: nonconformity, pollution, pollution quantification, indicators, standards

INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution, marine waters and lands, by oil residues represents an environmentally potential disaster, being strongly contaminated aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems, inclusive their flora and fauna (Sabău, Șandor, 2015).

Pollution of air, water and soil in the Barcău basin is due to anthropogenic activities carried out in production units that aim to exploit oil and gas fields and crude oil processing. The biggest environmental pollution problems in the Barcău basin are encountered in the Suplacu de Barcău locality, due to the drilling platforms, the extraction wells parks and the oil processing at the former S.C. Petrolsub S.A. (Josan et al., 2004).

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Crude oil extraction in the upper basin of the Barcău River has a tradition of over 50 years. The Extraction Scaffold from Suplacu de Barcău (currently S.C. Petrom S.A. Suplacu de Barcău) operates from 1960-1970.

The crude oil deposit on the Suplacu de Barcău structure is heavy and viscous, being cantonated in the base Pannonian, the depth at the end of the layer oscillating between 35 and 220 m. The productive layer is protected at the top of a marl with varying thicknesses between 3 and 20 m. The upper Pannonian is made up of alternating sandy marls, marshy sands, and even two layers of sand, with continuity throughout all the structure (Berchez, 2014).

The crude oil extracted from the deposits of the Suplac structure is of naphtheno - aromatic type, the non - cerous - asphalt - unsulphous group, having on average the following composition: molecular weight between 290 and 763; asphaltene content between 2.3 and 10 %; a paraffin content of between 6.5 and 7.3 % and a resin content of between 2.4 and 11.3 % (Sabău et al., 2011).

Due to their physico-chemical properties, extraction of crude oil in the Suplac structure is accomplished by two methods aimed at fluidization: steam injection into the productive layer (Fig. 1) and underground combustion.

Fig. 1. The exploitation of crude oil by injection of steam into the productive layer
(Source: Berchez, 2014)

Processing of crude oil extracted was carried out by the S.C. PETROSUB S.A. Suplacu de Barcău refinery until 2005, currently the production activity is stopped, the processing is carried out by other refineries in the country. After 2005 the extraction of crude oil is taken over

by S.C. CONCEPT S.A. Ploiești, Suplacul de Barcau section, which distributes crude oil to the refineries in the country, through C.F.R. (by rail), the crude oil supply at loading points is carried out through a pipeline network.

Monitoring of air, groundwater and surface water quality in industrial areas of large urban agglomerations has been the subject of research by Costea et al., 2017 and Romocea et al., 2018.

Air emissions from the oil and natural gas in hydraulic fracturing exploitations (Xu, Chen, 2016) and the environmental impact on air pollution from oil extraction and refining industry (Topi et al., 2012) are the main problems studied for air pollution.

Groundwater and surface water pollution with petroleum residues can occur, not only in the oil extraction fields, but also in the oil pipeline route or in the city's fuel supply stations (Scradaneanu et al., 2016).

The research of groundwater and surface water quality and respective air quality (Zhang et al., 2012) in oil holdings are of particular importance due to the impact on vegetable resources (Mogborukor, 2014; Aniefiok et al., 2018) and public health (Johnston et al., 2019).

In the case of groundwater pollution, the technologies used for pollution mitigation are very expensive, and in the last decades the methods of biological attenuation of pollutants concentration are increasingly being used (Purohit, 2006).

The Barcău hydrographical basin and the pollution of the environmental factors in the crude oil extraction area have been the subject of numerous research studies, such as: the study of climatic risks (Cristea, 2004), the quality of the Barcău river (Andrișca, 2011) and the ecological reconstruction of the soils polluted with crude oil (Colibaș et al., 1995; Șandor, 2011; Sabău, Șandor, 2013; Șandor et al., 2013; Sabău, Șandor, 2015).

The main objective of this work is to monitor the quality of the air and water, in the crude oil extraction perimeter of Suplacu de Barcău, in view of establishing the measures that are necessary for their protection.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In the period 1997-2013, the results of the non-compliance aspects for the air and water factors were investigated, as well as the elaboration of a set of measures necessary for the protection of air and water quality, the extraction scaffold, the Suplacu de Barcău structure.

The determination of the main physico-chemical indicators of air and water was performed according to ICIM Bucharest standards (Berchez et al., 2018).

The determination of air chemical parameters has as main objective the monitoring of the air quality in the polluted areas, in terms of establishing the influence that each source of pollution exerts on the air quality. The sampling of air samples was performed according to STAS 10331-1989. Depending on the nature of the pollutant and the harvesting possibilities, three sampling methods have been used: suction, closed bottling and sedimentation. The harvested samples were analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively according to STAS 12574-1987.

The investigation of the physico-chemical parameters of groundwater and surface water had as objective the verification of the concentration of the pollutants within the legal limits imposed by existing STAS.

Medium or point water samples were collected from the following locations: two wells from Suplacu de Barcău; waste water before entering in the treatment plant; waste water at the exit from the wastewater treatment and discharge into the Barcău River; from the Barcău River, downstream and upstream of the discharge point.

For the harvested waters the following physico-chemical properties pH (potentiometric method); Chemical oxygen consumption CCOCr (permanganometric method); Biochemical oxygen consumption CBO₅ (Winkler method); Filtration residue (filtration); The dry residue, MTS 105 °C (by evaporation); Fixed residue, MTS 600 °C (oven drying); Chlorides Cl (Mohr method); Ammonium NH₄, Nitrites NO₂, Nitrates NO₃ (photometric methods); Oil products (gravimetric method SR 7877-1); Sulfides and H₂S (iodometric method); Phenols (spectrophotometric method ISO:2003) were determined.

Depending on the results of the measurements, technical and organizational measures have been proposed for the prevention and combating of pollution of environmental factors (Cojocaru, 1995; Neag, 1997; Sabău, 2009).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result of non-conforming aspects of air, measures that are required for air protection

The main sources of air pollution are the emissions into the high atmosphere and accidental sources of emission combustion gases.

Sources of emissions to air at high level refer to: noxes from exhaust baskets of combustion gases from crude oil collection and separation parks (Fig. 2); the noxes discharged from the flue gas escape bins from the boiler batteries that play a role in the steady supply of the cyclical injection wells and, respectively, gas spills into the atmosphere from wells where crude oil exploitation is carried out by underground combustion.

The accidental sources of detected emissions of combustion gases refer to: craters in the southeastern area of the Suplacu de Barcău structure (permanent character) and reaction wells affected by underground combustion due to leakage of equipment.

Following studies on gas emissions to the atmosphere as a result of the oil extraction activity on the S.C. PETROM S.A. Suplacu de Barcău, the following non-conformities were found in accordance with the norms of the Environmental Legislation:

Fig. 2. Flue gas discharge basket at oil collection and separation parks
(Source: Berchez, 2014)

Concentration of air in carbon monoxide (CO):

- values of 7.5 mg/m^3 in the oil fields, thus exceeding the maximum admissible concentration of 6 mg/m^3 .

- values higher than 1.3 mg/m^3 , recorded on restricted areas outside the oil fields, in the direction of the dominant wind, in Foglaş, Leşmir, Şumal, Poř.

- the maximum permissible over 30 minutes are low, both in area and value.

Concentration of air in methane (CH₄) shows values $\approx 3 \text{ mg/m}^3$ in the territory of Suplac and values between 1 and 3 mg/m^3 in areas adjacent to Suplacu de Barcău. He does not have sanitary norms.

Concentration of air in nitrogen dioxide (NO₂):

• maximum admissible values of up to 0.4 mg/m^3 were recorded on the E - V directions in the northern area of Suplacu de Barcău (the maximum permissible concentration of 30 minutes being 0.3 mg/m^3).

- the limit for the average annual concentrations is not exceeded (0.04 mg/m³).

Concentration of particulate matter no exceedances of sanitary standards were found.

Concentration of air in volatile organic hydrocarbons:

- there were values of ≈ 12 mg/m³ in the area of Suplacu de Barcău, but also values of 3 - 5 mg/m³ in areas adjacent to Suplac, west of Leșmir and north of Valea Cerului. There is no sanitary norm.

Measures required to prevent and mitigate air pollution

The reduction and prevention of pollution of the atmosphere with noxious emissions resulting from the oil extraction process consists of a set of technical-organizational measures:

- continuous monitoring of the atmosphere of the extraction parks affected by internal combustion.
- monitoring and limiting the air injection pressure in the reservoir, to prevent airborne emissions.
- conditioning and evacuation of harmful gases from the underground combustion process, by conversion of CO to CO₂ periodic measurements of noxious gases to steam generating boilers.
- control and regulation of combustion gases so that noxious emissions lie below the maximum permissible concentration.
- removing leaks from the injection wells and reaction wells.

Result of non-compliance aspects for the water factor, measures required for water protection

The main sources of groundwater, surface and stagnant waters pollution for the area of Suplacu de Barcău are represented by: industrial waste waters; craters in the Suplac structure area (groundwater and combustion gases); leakages from the well column (crude oil and combustion gases); accidental leakage from sludge deposits; non-ecological wells; the proper failure of decanting dams arranged on the valleys; possible cracks and breaks on transport pipelines; accidental soil pollution with oil; faulty sewers in the industrial premises.

Pollution of groundwater and stagnant water for Suplacu de Barcău. The groundwater canvas is not related to the groundwater developed in the Barcău meadow, downstream of Balc.

In order to determine the existence of a certain degree of pollution in the groundwater and deep water, samples were taken from two wells, considered standard, in Suplacu de Barcău. The result of the analyzes is presented in Table 1.

The comparison of the values of the analyzed indicators with the STAS 1334/91 limits showed that they fall within the normal limits, without pollution at this level.

The physico-chemical characteristics of the water from the craters in the Southeast area of the exploitation (Table 2) show that they exceed the legal permissible limits, which are in accordance with STAS 4708-88 (surface water - Category III of rivers).

Table 1

Physico-chemical characteristics of the water from two wells in the Suplacu de Barcău locality (Source: processing after ICIM Bucharest)

Nr. crt.	Indicators	U.M.	Sample No 1 (F1)	Sample No 2 (F2)	Admitted Limits STAS 1334/91
1	pH	-	7.5	7.2	6.5-7.4
2	CCO-Mn	mg/l	1.8	2.3	2.5
3	Filtrable residue	mg/l	256	292	100-800
4	Chlorides	mg/l	42	48	250
5	Sulphates	mg/l	36	51	200
6	Ammonium	mg/l	0	0	0
7	Nitrites	mg/l	0	0	0
8	Nitrates	mg/l	2.8	4.3	45
9	Phenols	mg/l	0	0	0.001
10	Petroleum products	mg/l	0	0	0
11	Calcium	mg/l	52.3	56.5	100
12	Magnesium	mg/l	11.9	14.3	50
13	Total hardness	mg/l	6.9	7.1	20

Table 2

The physico-chemical characteristics of the water from the craters in the Southeast area of the exploitation (Source: processing after ICIM Bucharest)

Nr. crt.	Indicators	U.M.	Old crater	New crater	Admitted Limits
1	pH	-	6.2	6.4	6.5-8.5
2	CCOCr	mg/l	627	314	30
3	CBO ₅	mg/l	117	50	12
4	Filtrable residue	mg/l	984	1272	1200
5	Sulphates	mg/l	91	101	400
6	Chlorides	mg/l	206	354	300
7	Ammonium	mg/l	10.8	5.4	10
8	Phosphorus	mg/l	0.7	0.2	0.1
9	Phenols	mg/l	0	0	0.05
10	Extractables Substances	mg/l	40	18	-
11	Sulfides and H ₂ S	mg/l	0.2	0	0.1

Stagnant waters constitute a potential source of accidental pollution of the Barcău River, of lesser importance, and an isolated character, which is manifested at low frequencies.

Pollution of surface waters represented by the main water courses, affected by the pollution of petroleum products, resulting from the production of the Petrol Scaffolding. These are: Frumoasa (Fig. 3), Borumlaca Valley brooks and the Barcău River, where industrial wastewaters from the treatment plant are discharged.

Fig. 3. Waste water discharges into the Frumoasa Valley
(Source: Berchez, 2014)

The main cause of pollution of surface and ground water is the discharge of industrial waste water. In order to quantify the effect on surface waters, especially on the waters of the Barcău River. The physical and chemical characteristics of the industrial waste waters were observed at the entrance to the treatment plant and to the discharge into the Barcău River (Table 3).

The evolution of the waste water purification indicators on the period 2009-2013 and the evolution of the Barcău River contamination indicators, upstream and downstream of the oil industry, for the period 2010-2013 are studied (Table 4).

From the analysis of the physico-chemical characteristics and the evolution of the industrial waste water purification indicators (Table 4), there are major overruns in all the monitored indicators.

Table 3

Physical and chemical characteristics of industrial waste water in the years 2010-2011
(Source: processing after ICIM Bucharest)

Analytical parameters	UM	Physico-chemical characteristics				Accepted limits
		Entry station		Exit station		
		2010	2011	2010	2011	
pH	-	7.4	6.8	7.8	7.3	6.8-8.5
CCOCr	mg/l	1484	1177	1143	877	-
CBO ₅	mg/l	483	371	343	272	15
MTS 105 °C	mg/l	611	914	98	314	40
MTS 600 °C	mg/l	116	101	69	166	40
MTS volatile	mg/l	81	89	29	47	40
Filtrable residue	mg/l	1988	1968	1556	1803	1200
Chloride	mg/l	538	395	389	338	-
Ammonium	mg/l	23.4	18.1	14.5	10.8	-
Nitrites	mg/l	0.26	0.17	0.15	0.07	-
Nitrates	mg/l	6,87	5.35	3.42	1.66	-
Oil products	mg/l	115	235	14	19	-
Sulfides and H ₂ S	mg/l	0.34	2.12	0.13	1.2	-
Phenols	mg/l	3.4	3.2	2.9	2.26	0.05
Total iron	mg/l	0.294	0.301	0.152	-	-
Phosphorus	mg/l	0.13	0.17	0.08	0.1	-

Table 4

Evolution of the pollution impurities indicators of treated industrial waste water discharged into the Barcău river in the period 2009-2013
(Source: processing after ICIM Bucharest)

Nr. crt	Effluent analyzed	The year	Analyzed Indicators					
			pH	CBO ₅ mg/l	MTS mg/l	Products oil mg/l	Phenols mg/l	Residue filterable mg/l
1	Industrial waste waters	2009	7.2 – 8.0	217	129	5.9	6.0	1556
2		2010	7.0 – 8.0	241	168	8.0	5.9	1445
3		2011	7.0 – 8.3	206	152	5.8	5.8	1748
4		2012	7.3 – 7.8	276	187	6.2	3.1	1485
5		2013	7.0 – 7.8	103	106	5.6	2.3	1645
Admitted limits			6.5 – 8.5	15.00	40.00	1.00	0.05	1200

The evolution of the indicators of pollution of Barcău river upstream and downstream of the Suplacu de Barcău oil exploitation, for the period 2010-2013, is presented in Table 5.

Due to the dilution recorded after the discharge of the treated waste water into the Barcau river, the values of the main physico-chemical indicators monitored (Table 4 and 5) fall within the permissible limits, being below the maximum values of STAS 4706-88, Category III rivers.

The only exceedances are recorded on the "petroleum products" indicator, which exceeds the admissible value by 5 times.

Table 5

Evolution of Barcău River Pollution Indicators upstream and downstream of Suplacu de Barcău Petroleum Exploration, for the period 2010 - 2013

(Source: processing after ICIM Bucharest)

Analytical parameters	UM	2010		2011		2012		2013		Limits STAS 4706-88
		Up	Down	Up	Down	Up	Down	Up	Down	
pH	-	7.3-7.7	7.3-7.7	6.6-7.8	7.0-8.3	7.5-8.2	7.0-8.2	7.2-8.1	7.6-8.0	6.5-8.5
CCOMn	mg/l	6.3	10.8	4.6	10.8	4.0	11.6	2.1	5.4	25
CBO ₅	mg/l	5.2	9.3	7.2	9.7	6.2	4.9	2.5	8.1	12
O ₂ dissolves.	mg/l	10.9	5.5	10.9	6.3	11.9	5.8	-	-	4
Residue	mg/l	236	336	207	314	231	436	154	290	1200
Filters. chloride	mg/l	23	59	20	46	21	80	10	24	300
Sulphates	mg/l	38	45	43	40	44	43	34	46	400
Ammonium	mg/l	0.51	1.32	0.61	1.79	0.86	0.98	0.18	0.7	10
Phenols	mg/l	0.013	0.034	0.006	0.045	0.024	0.013	-	0.06	0.05
Product. tanker	mg/l	-	0.4	0.16	0.54	-	0.65	-	0.46	0.1
Iron	mg/l	0.67	0.76	0.72	0.43	0.28	0.56	-	0.59	1.0
Calcium	mg/l	39.7	43.9	32.7	35.5	36.3	37.5	-	-	300
Magnesium	mg/l	7.1	9.1	6.9	12.2	11.6	13.8	-	-	200
Sodium	mg/l	23.2	73.8	22.6	39.7	35.2	83.2	-	-	200

Measures required to prevent pollution of surface water

The prevention of pollution of water courses with oil and residues resulting from various stages of oil exploitation consists of a set of technical and organizational measures:

- increasing the efficiency of the treatment plant;
- identifying sources of accidental pollution, stopping discharges and removing them;
- establishing a set of emergency measures for accidental pollution;
- regular inspection of water courses downstream of oil exploration;
- periodic monitoring of effluents in the Barcău River, respectively surface water quality control;
- training of intervention staff.

CONCLUSIONS

The extraction of crude oil in the upper basin of the Barcău River has a tradition of over 50 years, the extraction scaffold from Suplacu de Barcău, now S.C. Petrom S.A. operates from the 1960s to the 1970s.

The main sources of air pollution at the Suplacu de Barcău extraction scaffold are: high-altitude emissions (combustion gases discharge basket and flue gas from boiler batteries) and accidental emissions of combustion gases (craters in the Southeast area of the structure and wells affected by leakage from underground combustion due to the equipment).

For compliance with the legal limits of CO coming from underground combustion process is proposed the conversion of CO to CO₂ and periodic measurements of noxious gases to steam generating boilers.

Due to the fact that in the area of Suplacu de Barcău, the first groundwater does not reach the surface of the land, there are no exceedances of the legal limits of the pollutants analyzed in the groundwater.

The main cause of pollution of surface water is the discharge of industrial waste water, resulting from the production of the Petroleum Scaffolding.

The physico-chemical characteristics of the industrial waste waters indicates exceedances of the permissible legal limits, observed at the entrance to the treatment plant for both years of observations (2010 and 2011) at: CBO₅ (more than 25 times); Phenols (over 64 times); MTS 105 °C (over 25 times); MTS 600 °C and volatile MTS (more than 2 times); and respectively, Filtrable residue.

Although the values of the pollutant concentration in the waste water at the waste water treatment plant are improving, the waters discharged into the Barcau River still show exceedances of the maximum admissible values. Between 2009 and 2013, there were reductions in the concentration of pollutants reported, but not within the maximum admissible limits.

Due to the dilution recorded after the discharge of the treated waste water into the Barcau river, the values of the main physico-chemical indicators monitored fall within the permissible limits, being below the maximum values of STAS 4706-88, Category III rivers, except the “petroleum products” indicator, which exceeds the admissible value by 5 times.

The main technical and organizational measures necessary to prevent the pollution of the Barcau River are: the increasing the efficiency of the treatment plant, identifying the sources of accidental pollution, stopping discharges and removing them.

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SPECTRAL EVALUATION OF THE EFFECT OF POULTRY MANURE PELLETS ON PIGMENT CONTENT OF MAIZE (*ZEA MAYS L.*) AND WHEAT (*TRITICUM AESTIVUM L.*) SEEDLINGS

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Abstract

In my research I observed the effects of different poultry manure pellets on germination and pigment changes in maize and wheat with breeding test. At the end of the experiments I measured the pigment and spectral data. The effect of the pellets on the pigment content was also studied by Tukey's variance analysis and I evaluated the connection between pigment content and reflectance. Then based on the spectral data, principal component analysis was performed to select the appropriate wavelength ranges.

In the case of maize, the Natur extra and Nitro-plusz poultry manure pellets produced outstanding results on sandy soil and we can raise. In the case of wheat, the P+K manure pellets produced outstanding results. The absorption of chlorophyll can be measured at 678 nm and chlorophyll b at 650 nm. When we carried out the principal component analysis, we could select the 520-650 nm wavelength range and 700 nm wavelength for maize. For wheat the wavelengths were 540-650 nm and 702 nm. The priority ranges and their proximity ranges may be suitable for spectral monitoring of the pigment content.

Key words: wheat, maize, germ test, spectral monitoring

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, proper emphasis must be placed on the proper nutrient supply of plants in plant cultivation, because the good fertilization increases soil fertility, thereby increasing the quantity and quality of yields. In recent years, the use of organic fertilizers has come to the forefront in agriculture, and the certification of these products is mainly tested in germ cell cultures in pot. Studying germination is a difficult project, because germination processes vary widely between different seeds (Bewlely, 1997), while it is a cheap technology for measuring the nutritional quality of cereals (Paucar-Menacho et al., 2016).

The disadvantage is that most experiments are chemical, material and time-consuming. Spectral measurements can also be used to measure the content of the plants in the pots without sampling, in addition more economical and with the large area, the chlorophyll concentration of the leaf can be measured (Filella et al., 1995) In the past two decades, spectral material testing has also been introduced as a tool for agricultural drought, agricultural water flow factors and the resulting yield and quality assessment (Tamás et al., 2015; Nagy et al., 2018).

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The spectral analysis of the plant is a generally suitable for measuring the combination of plant pigments, especially chlorophyll and biomass (Hall et al., 2002; Huang et al., 2007). With this method, can be measured electromagnetic waves between 400-7500 nm, and in plants the photosynthetic pigments of the leaves are absorbed in the red band. Water, nutrients, carbon and plant pigments can be measured between 400-2500 nm in the spectrum (Nagy, 2014).

In my research, because of my role in food, I chose the two most important cereal crops in the world, corn and wheat, which must meet the growing needs of the world's population (Antal, 2005; Nagy, 2007; Bandici et al., 2011). I investigated the maize (*Zea mays L.*) and wheat (*Triticum aestivum L.*) on the germination of different poultry manure pellets method of spectrophotometrically and spectrally.

First of all, the change in the content of pigment (chlorophyll and carotenoid) in test plants was important, because chlorophyll content provides information on the nitrogen content of the plant, which is related to photosynthesis (Nagy, 2014). Tóth et al., 2002 reported that the concentration of chlorophyll in the agricultural maize leaf decreased while carotenoid increased by reducing the amount of nitrogen.

Water demand of maize increases as plants forward in growth, this period during this time, soil moisture will ensure the connection between fertilization and grain formation and the transport of minerals to the right place (Domuța, 2015). Wheat is a far more feasible version of remote sensing for analyzing nitrogen than using other laboratory tests (Filella et al., 1995).

The main objective of the research was the effect of the examined poultry manure pellets on the change of maize and wheat seed pigment content, the spectral detection and correlation of the pigment content with the spectrophotometric measurement method and the selection of the spectral wavelength for the pigment content measurement.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

We used 8 kinds of soil improvers were examined for maize seedlings and for 6 weeks on maize plants (provided by the Institute of Agrochemical and Soil Science (ATI)) and wheat seedlings on the basis of changes in plant pigment content during my research. In addition, I made a preliminary assessment of whether the pigment content could be determined by non-invasive spectral measurements, which could determine the effect of pellets on plants with material-energy and time-saving.

During the experiment with maize and wheat germ I used 7 fermented poultry manure pellets and one type of fertilizer were applied at a dose of 1 t / ha and 1.5 t / ha with 4 x set repetition. At the setting of the experiment,

have been filled 1 l of pots of 1 kg of undisturbed sand soil and added to which the pellets of poultry manure were at 700 grams.

The used poultry manure pellets are: Natur (100 % fermented poultry manure), Natur extra (Fermented poultry manure + meat flour), Kali - sulf (Fermented poultry manure + potassium sulphate), Kali - plus (Fermented poultry manure + Potassium chloride), Phosphorus - plus (Fermented Poultry Fertilizer + Phosphorus), P + K (Fermented Poultry Fertilizer + Phosphorus + Potassium), Nitro - plus (Fermented Poultry Fertilizer + Urea), Nitro - plus 2 (Fermented Poultry Fertilizer + Diammonium Phosphate) they were.

Soil moisture content was set at 60 % of the soil's open ground water capacity (CW) and daily irrigation replaced the missing water. We sown 5 seeds in maize and 10 seeds in wheat at every pots on 2 cm depth and after 14 days we weighed the plants pigment content and spectral characteristics.

Spectral measurements of our seedlings were carried out under laboratory conditions with AVASPEC 2048 spectrometer at a wavelength range of 400-1000 nm with an accuracy of 0.6 nm.

To determine the total content of chlorophyll and carotenoid we need fresh plant samples always. Samples should be destroyed in a mortar with quartz sand and acetone until a homogeneous state is reached, then settled in a Hettich ROTOFIX 32A centrifuge. The absorbance of the samples was measured in a glass cuvette at a wavelength of 470 nm, 644 nm and 663 nm in a spectrophotometer.

The values we have obtained are described by Droppa et al., 2003 can be converted to chlorophyll values and Lichtenthaler et al., 1983 can be used to determine the content of carotenoids, chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b.

The obtained chlorophyll, carotenoid and chlorophyll results were grouped and did statistical analysis with SPSS software. We calculated the statistical differences between control and treatment pigment results with 5 % significance by Tukey's variance analysis. In order to identify the wavelengths that can be used to determine the most important and pigment content, spectral data were grouped according to their chlorophyll content. I analyzed the average and standard deviation of the groups. In addition, the most sensitive wavelength ranges change of pigment content were selected by the main component analysis of spectral data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of poultry manure pellets on corn pigment content

The chlorophyll content of maize seedlings was $1683 \pm 319 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$, and the chlorophyll content of our maize plant for 6 weeks gave $1530 \pm 405 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$ taking into account all added poultry manure pellets. Chlorophyll

content of the maize seedlings used for the control, which did not contain added soil improvers was $1472 \pm 385 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$ and in the other case $1478 \pm 213 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$. The carotenoid content of maize seedlings during treatment was $305 \pm 50 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$ and the maize plant for 6 weeks gave $416 \pm 88 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$ which is higher than the control at $267 \pm 63 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$ and $442 \pm 34 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$.

It can be stated that poultry manure pellets have a positive effect on the physiological processes of corn. During the treatments, the NH_4NO_3 proved to be the most effective, and organic matter can be highlighted in terms of supply Natur extra and Nitro - plus 1-2 addition.

Both abiotic and biotic stress effects have an effect on both chlorophyll and carotenoid concentrations, the plant pigments begin to decline. This statement is closely related to the maize seedlings, the concentration of chlorophyll was decreased, while the carotenoid increases proportionally with the reduction of nitrogen ($R^2 = 0.9088$, $p < 0.05$).

The pigment changes resulting from the stress effects are significantly correlated between the carotenoid -chlorophyll ratio and the chlorophyll content, there was a weak correlation between values ($R^2 = 0.267$, $p < 0.05$).

Different effects of different treatments on the change of the content of maize seedlings in the chlorophyll can be distinguished by different effects on the basis of multivariate analysis of variance ($p = 0.000$). We got higher levels of control yielded 1 t / ha and 1.5 t / ha NH_4NO_3 , Natur extra, Nitro - plus, Phospho - plus, and P + K treatments.

The ratio of carotenoid and chlorophyll to maize seed $0.182 \pm 0.012 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$ is the treatment, which is not significantly different from the chlorophyll value of $0.185 \pm 0.009 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$ in the control, the treatments generally gave a control value. Differential effects can be distinguished from multiple variance analysis during statistical analysis ($p = 0.000$) (Table 1).

The value of R^2 was also significant in the corn grown for 6 weeks in the case of the chlorophyll carotenoid ratio was $R^2 = 0.88844$, $p < 0.05$.

The correlation between the carotenoid - chlorophyll ratio and the chlorophyll content in the pigment change due to the stress effects gave a value of $R^2 = 0.5268$, $p < 0.05$ so the correlation is medium.

Different chlorophyll containing treatments can be separated based on multivariate variance analysis ($p = 0.027$). The Nitro - plus 1, Nitro - plus 2 and P + K treatments was given statistically higher result for the control, while the other used pellets produced nearly the same results as the control. The ratio of carotenoids to chlorophyll during treatments was $0.299 \pm 0.021 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$ so gave a positive result compared to $0.296 \pm 0.016 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$ of chlorophyll. Differential effects can be distinguished from multiple variance analysis during statistical analysis ($p = 0.000$) (Table 2).

Table 1

Differences in chlorophyll content differences and carotenoid / chlorophyll ratio between treatments

	Mean	Stand. deviat	Min	Max	Mean	Stand. deviat	Min	Max
NH ₄ NO ₃ 1 t/ha	2163 c	375	1603	2638	0.181 b	0.006	0.174	0.188
NH ₄ NO ₃ 1.5 t/ha	2007 c	154	1824	2249	0.171 a	0.005	0.165	0.179
phospho plus 1 t/ha	1508 ab	226	1208	1845	0.198 c	0.013	0.183	0.218
phospho plus 1.5 t/ha	1848 bc	145	1674	2066	0.177 ab	0.004	0.171	0.181
kali plus 1 t/ha	1398 a	132	1260	1609	0.176 ab	0.009	0.162	0.186
kali plus 1.5 t/ha	1518 ab	181	1259	1715	0.173 a	0.007	0.163	0.181
kali sulf 1 t/ha	1321 a	181	1044	1549	0.190 bc	0.007	0.18	0.197
kali sulf 1.5 t/ha	1755 bc	98	1658	1909	0.169 a	0.002	0.166	0.172
natur 1 t/ha	1570 ab	173	1403	1810	0.187 bc	0.006	0.18	0.197
natur 1.5 t/ha	1332 a	147	1126	1539	0.199 c	0.018	0.182	0.225
natur extra 1.5 t/ha	1852 bc	471	1104	2398	0.178 ab	0.004	0.173	0.183
natur extra 1 t/ha	1805 bc	229	1623	2196	0.179 ab	0.007	0.175	0.191
nitro plus 1 t/ha	1829 bc	310	1360	2149	0.177 ab	0.013	0.156	0.19
nitro plus 1.5 t/ha	1829 bc	185	1645	2097	0.183 b	0.01	0.173	0.2
P+K 1 t/ha	1521 ab	183	1210	1678	0.197 c	0.012	0.188	0.217
P+K 1.5 t/ha	1629 bc	300	1354	2030	0.182 b	0.005	0.177	0.188
control	1472 a	352	1106	1871	0.183 b	0.007	0.179	0.2

* where there is no statistical difference between treatments with the same letter value

Table 2

Differences in chlorophyll content and carotenoid / chlorophyll ratio between treatments during 6 weeks of cultivation in corn

	Mean	Stand. deviation	Min	Max	Mean	Stand. deviation	Min	Max
control	1528 ab	173	1327	1629	0.296 c	0.016	0.286	0.315
natur	1292 ab	234	1106	1556	0.286 c	0.009	0.281	0.296
natur extra	1390 a	259	1098	1594	0.271 abc	0.022	0.25	0.294
kali sulf	1430 ab	285	1177	1741	0.290 c	0.026	0.267	0.318
kali plus	1214 a	187	1080	1428	0.291 c	0.016	0.282	0.31
nitro plus 1	2209 b	200	1986	2372	0.237 a	0.005	0.232	0.242
phospho plus	1330 ab	190	1191	1547	0.279 bc	0.009	0.27	0.287
P+K	1701 ab	325	1439	2065	0.308 c	0.007	0.303	0.317
nitro plus 2	1888 b	519	1379	2418	0.244 a	0.011	0.232	0.253

* where there is no statistical difference between treatments with the same letter value

Effect of poultry manure pellets on the pigment content of wheat plants

The chlorophyll content of wheat seedling with the added soil improvers was $1917 \pm 266 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$ and the control shows a positive increase

compared to the content of $1770 \pm 235 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$ chlorophyll. The wheat seedling carotenoid content after treatment was $318 \pm 56 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$ and the control value was $295 \pm 63 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$.

On the basis of our values, it can be stated that the added soil improvers have a positive effect on the development and physiological processes of wheat seedlings. P + K proved to be the most effective during the treatments and the NH_4NO_3 , Kali - sulf, Kali - plus and Nitro - plus granules were the most important in terms of results.

Various abiotic and biotic stress effects on wheat seedlings also influence the change in pigment content. There is a moderately close contest between the reduction in chlorophyll and carotenoid content ($R^2 = 0.604$, $p < 0.05$).

The resulting pigment changes were not significant in the case of wheat seedlings in relation to the correlations between the carotenoid - chlorophyll ratio and the chlorophyll content.

The effects of the chlorophyll content can be statistically separated from the wheat seedlings in the multivariate variance analysis ($p = 0.001$). The NH_4NO_3 , P + K, Nitro - plus and Kali - plus treatments gave higher results compared to control for both doses. Calculating the carotenoid and chlorophyll ratios on all treatments were $0.16 \pm 0.019 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$, which is no significant difference compared to $0.16 \pm 0.012 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$ of control. We can be separated statistically different groups according to the carotenoid chlorophyll ratio based on the multivariate variance analysis ($p = 0.000$) (Table 3).

Evaluation of the spectral measurement of pigment content in maize and wheat foliage

In order to investigate the spectral properties of maize and wheat, the reflectance standard deviations calculated for chlorophyll content were compared by proportioning the given reflectance averages. The examined groups cover intervals containing spectral data of all plants from the scattering of low chlorophyll-containing reflectance data.

There was a high standard deviation from 510 to 530 nm, the standard deviation of reflectance increased with the chlorophyll content, there is a high standard of variation in high chlorophyll-containing maize in germ and breeding plants and in wheat seedlings, this range may be suitable for determining plant maturity tests. The peak of the scatter is outstanding due to the absorption properties of chlorophyll measured in the given wavelength range and sensitive to low chlorophyll content at 680 nm.

The groups have to give an almost equal value of the standard deviation of the reflectance measured at 680 nm on the basis of the literature, which is not justified for wheat seedlings. The reflectance values

measured at wavelength ranges from 678 nm to 30 nm showed high variability, so this wavelength range can be used to measure pigment content values. The reflectance values measured in the NIR range showed low variability, this wavelength range can be used to measure pigment content values. The reflectance scatter values measured at 525-575 nm and 700 nm wavelengths are pigment sensitive for both plants in our chart.

Table 3

Differences in chlorophyll content differences and carotenoid / chlorophyll ratio between treatments

	Mean	Stand deviation	Min	Max	Mean	Stand deviation	Min
NH ₄ NO ₃ 1 t/ha	1978 c	242	1568	2130	0.162 bc	0.154	0.173
NH ₄ NO ₃ 1.5 t/ha	2180 cd	304	1838	2670	0.164 bc	0.162	0.202
phospho plus 1 t/ha	1853 b	93	1758	1996	0.143 a	0.124	0.157
phospho plus 1.5 t/ha	1849 b	118	1666	1979	0.179 d	0.169	0.185
kali plus 1 t/ha	1860 b	302	1400	2226	0.142 a	0.135	0.147
kali plus 1.5 t/ha	2067 c	322	1534	2329	0.166 bc	0.168	0.182
kali sulf 1 t/ha	2056 cd	142	1861	2223	0.138 a	0.127	0.152
kali sulf 1.5 t/ha	1637 a	111	1523	1770	0.178 cd	0.173	0.187
natur 1 t/ha	1759 ab	80	1649	1837	0.153 ab	0.135	0.169
natur 1.5 t/ha	1889 b	326	1344	2195	0.186 d	0.174	0.201
natur extra 1 t/ha	1676 ab	145	1455	1815	0.161 bc	0.145	0.17
natur extra 1.5 t/ha	1843 b	291	1416	2172	0.179 d	0.173	0.184
nitro plus 1 t/ha	1888 b	300	1676	2404	0.175 cd	0.163	0.194
nitro plus 1.5 t/ha	1986 c	155	1849	2234	0.148 a	0.168	0.197
P+K 1 t/ha	2336 cd	236	2040	2595	0.143 a	0.09	0.162
P+K 1.5 t/ha	1959 c	175	1721	2215	0.146 a	0.173	0.197
control	1770 ab	204	1569	2110	0.165 bc	0.154	0.183

* where there is no statistical difference between treatments with the same letter value

The maize and wheat main component analysis can be used to raise 3 wavelengths: 520 nm, 650 nm and 700 nm (Fig. 1).

CONCLUSIONS

The studied soil fertilizer pellets have a positive effect on the physiological processes of maize based on the analysis of maize pigment content. For maize production, the use of Phosphorus- plus, Kali-sulf soil improvers is recommended for poultry manure pellets at doses of Natur extra, Nitro-plus 1 and Nitro-plus 2 and 1.5 t / ha. Based on these, it can be that high-nitrogen pellets produce positive results in maize production,

including additives that are supplemented with urea and DAP. During the development of potassium additive, maize will be added and utilized later.

Fig. 1. Relative standard deviation and main component analysis of the reflectance of maize and wheat

The use of KCl as an additive is to be avoided due to the presumed sensitivity of the chloride to the plant.

The wheat seed pigment content confirmed the positive effect of poultry manure pellets on physiological processes like maize. According to the treatments, the used of the P + K in wheat production is the most suitable, and the used of Kali- sulf, Kali-plus and Nitro-plus poultry manure pellets is also recommended. Based on these, it is recommended to use higher nitrogen and potassium-containing organic additives in pellet production in the future.

The non-invasive determination of chlorophyll content can be suggested in the carotenoid -sensitive 520-580 nm wavelength range, as well as the reflectance values measured at 650 nm and 700 nm. Spectral measurement can be used to examine changes in pigment content in products therefore, it is recommended that the spectrophotometric method be supplemented with spectral measurements in the future. The use of spectral measurements can provide a basis for the development of field

methodology as well, since the given test parameters can be measured without destruction in the field.

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EFFECTS OF ALGAE PRODUCTS ON NUTRIENT UPTAKE AND FRUIT QUALITY OF APPLE

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Abstract

Nowadays the main task of scientists and farmers is to find natural ways to avoid negative effects of climatic anomalies and improve plant productivity lead to environmental friendly agriculture.

Biostimulants have a great potential to achieve these aims but unfortunately there is little information about its application in apple growing mostly in East Hungary.

*For this reason, foliar nutrition experiment was made in the region of Nyírség (East Hungary) to investigate the effect of different biostimulants (algae products) on yield, leaf nutrient concentration and quality parameters of cv. 'Gala Must' apple (*Malus domestica* Borkh.) variety. The study was conducted in 2012 at Nyírbátor in East Hungary in a 14 years old apple plantation. Treatments (application time and doses) were adjusted to the phenological phases of apple and the control was used an untreated check. Effect of treatments was monitored by leaf diagnosis and apple quality measurements.*

The results demonstrate that the treatments increased the external fruit parameters (diameter, weight, shape index) but not affected consequently the leaf macronutrient status compared to the control. We suppose that, stable treatment effect on leaf nutrient status can be observed in long-lasting experiment only. The applied products significantly increased the amount of flavonoid and phenolic compounds and water soluble antioxidant capacity value compared to the control. Our fruit analysis results supported that the applied biostimulators had no effect on fruit acid and ash content. Moreover, the applied products resulted higher sugar, vitamin C and dry matter content despite the unfavourable, very dry climatic conditions. In sum, results showed that foliar application of biostimulants had a positive effect on yield and resulted bigger and healthier therefore more marketable fruits.

Key words: algae based biostimulants, fruit nutrition, fruit quality, nutrient uptake

INTRODUCTION

Global demographic pressure and unexpected climatic events and their growing rate on agricultural production calls for novel and sustainable approaches toward satisfying the ever-growing demand for plant biomass destined for human food, animal feed, and energy production. Conventional agricultural practice has relied overwhelmingly on non-renewable inputs of fertilizers and pesticides (Calvo et al., 2014).

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Currently, legislation restricts the use of mineral fertilizers and pesticides and thus forces a new approach to reducing the use of chemical products through either parallel application or partial replacement with formulations capable of enhancing the efficiency of conventional treatment. Feeding a growing population requires yield increases and enhanced crop quality, both of which are fostered by biostimulants (European Biostimulant Industry Council (EBIC), 2012; Jardin, 2015; Chiaiese et al., 2018).

Plant biostimulants (PBs) attract interest in modern agriculture as a tool to enhance crop performance, resilience to environmental stress, and nutrient use efficiency (Bulgari et al., 2014).

According to recent EU Regulation, PBs are defined mainly through their claimed action, therefore PBs encompass diverse organic and inorganic substances (humic acids and protein hydrolysates) as well as prokaryotes (e.g., plant growth promoting bacteria) and eukaryotes such as mycorrhiza, N-fixing bacteria and macroalgae (seaweed) (European Commission, 2016; Yakhin et al., 2017; Chiaiese et al., 2018).

Among the natural materials of such capability are algae, which contain a variety of biologically active compounds verified to have a beneficial influence on plants (Balconi, 2012; Dmytryk, Chojnacka, 2018). Algae are increasing crops' performance, optimizing qualitative traits, reinforcing abiotic stress resistance and recovery, give greater profitability for the farmers. Biostimulants can enhance quality attributes of produce, including sugar content, colour, fruit seeding, etc. Enhanced quality can mean higher incomes for farmers, better storage and more nutritious food for consumers (Khan et al., 2009; Khan et al., 2012; Battacharyya et al., 2015).

Biostimulants foster plant growth and development throughout the crop life cycle from seed germination to plant maturity in a number of demonstrated ways, including but not limited to:

- Improving the efficiency of the plant's metabolism to induce yield increases and enhanced crop quality;
- Increasing plant tolerance to and recovery from abiotic stresses;
- Facilitating nutrient assimilation, translocation and use;
- Enhancing quality attributes of produce, including sugar content, colour, fruit seeding, etc.;
- Rendering water use more efficient;
- Enhancing soil fertility, particularly by fostering the development of complementary soil micro-organisms.

Moreover, biostimulants help protect and improve soil health by fostering the development of beneficial soil microorganisms. Healthier soil retains water more effectively and better resists erosion (Dudás et al., 2017).

To handle limiting factors and to insure high quality crops in the future lot of authors recommend the using of plant biostimulants to enhance nutrition efficiency, abiotic stress tolerance and/or crop quality traits, regardless of its nutrients content (Khan et al., 2009; Balconi, 2012; European Biostimulant Industry Council (EBIC), 2012; Battacharyya et al., 2015; Jardin, 2015). Their use provides an opportunity for growers to mitigate and correct the increasing effects of abiotic stress situations.

Furthermore, biostimulants contribute to socio-economic development. By making existing agricultural practices more efficient and improving post-harvest storage, biostimulants help reduce waste throughout the agri-food chain. Less waste means lower costs, which ultimately benefit the consumer who has access to high-quality, affordable food (European Biostimulant Industry Council (EBIC), 2012). The proper orchard management practises are the main key factors in the production of high and qualitative yields of fruits (Bramlage, 1993; Nagyné Demeter, 2010; Nagy et al., 2016).

In Hungary, in recent years, there has been a growing perception of the strengthening of the ecological approach in fruit nutrient management (Demeter, 2014), which requires the use of environmentally conscious cultivation technologies based on biostimulants.

The aim of this paper is to provide further data about biostimulants applying and their effects on yield and fruit quality. We wanted to study how effect the algae treatments on the mineral uptake of apple trees and the internal and external parameters of apples.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study was performed at the orchard of F.N. Fruit Ltd. at Nyírbátor in 2012. Comparison and evaluation of the effects of different biostimulants were performed in our study. The orchard was planted in 1998, grafted on M26 rootstock. Spacing between and within rows was 4.85 x 1.6 m. The apple cultivar was Gala Must. The orchard has drip irrigation system.

Applied treatments

In the experiment, beside the control, four algae biostimulants (Globalga, Goemar BM 86, Organic Green Gold (OGG) and Wuxal ascofol) were used to test their effects on fruit yield and quality.

Globalga is a reddish-brownish seaweed liquid, pH is 6.5 (in 10 % solution), contains: 7.0 % N and P₂O₅, 4.0 % K₂O, 6.0 % amino acids and EDTA as additives.

Goemar BM 86 is basically *Ascophyllum nodosum*, contains GA 142 algae cream, 1.67 % N, 9.6 % SO₃, 4.8 % MgO, 0.02 % Mo and 2.0 % B.

OGG is basically *Chlorella vulgaris*, green suspension, pH is 6.25 dry matter contain is 1 %, contains: 0.15 % N, 0.29 % P₂O₅, 0.25 % K₂O, 0.035 % Ca, 0.02 % Mg, 0.008 % B and 0.015 % Fe.

Wuxal ascofol is 50 % algae suspension, contains: 2.3 % N, 1.5 % K₂O, 0.195 % CaO, 0.033 % MgO, 3 % B, 0.005 % Fe, 0.5 % Zn, iodine, plant hormones.

The treatments were set up in three replications. Twenty trees per replication were treated. Algae products were sprayed on the foliage of the selected trees by a motorized knapsack sprayer. Applied dosages and the circumstances* of the application are showed in Table 1.

Table 1

Time and dosages of the applied treatments (l/acre)

Phenological stages	Application Time	Globalga	Goemar BM 86	Organic Green Gold	Wuxal ascofol
half blooming	26 th April	2.0	3.0	3.0	-
Full blooming	30 th April	2.0	3.0	3.0	10.0
Petal falling	4 th May	2.0	3.0	3.0	-
2 week after full blooming	11 th May	2.0	3.0	3.0	-
3 week after full blooming	18 th May	-	-	-	10.0
4 week after full blooming	27 th May	-	-	-	10.0

*- treatments were adjusted to the instructions of the manufacturers

Soil sampling and preparation and results

As the root system was most concentrated in the upper layer of the soil, soil samples were taken from 0-30 and 30-60 cm layers of the soil by using manual soil sampling equipment as described in Jackson (1958) using the Hungarian standard method MSZ-08 0202-77. Sampling was performed before the experiments were set up. The samples were dried, sieved, homogenized and stored in plastic boxes until the examination.

Soil pH was determined from a soil solution of 0.01 M CaCl₂. Plasticity index (K_A) and humus content were measured according to Hungarian guideline (MSZ 20135:1999). Nitrogen forms of each soil sample were quantified according to Houba et al. (1986). For extracting the available P and K content of soils, ammonium-lactate solution (so called AL extractant) was used, then the amount of phosphorus was quantified colorimetrically with the phosphomolybdovanadate method (Hungarian standard MSZ 20135:1999). Potassium content was quantified by flame atom emission spectrophotometry (Hungarian standard MSZ 20135: 1999). For determining Ca, Mg, Mn, Cu and Zn contents of the soil Lakanen-Erviö solution (LE) was used (Lakanen, Erviö, 1971). Soil Ca, Mg, Mn, Cu and

Zn contents were quantified using flame atomic absorption spectrophotometry (Hungarian standard MSZ 20135: 1999).

The results of soil analysis are showed in Table 2. Orchard soil type was slightly acidic, non-calcareous sandy soil with very low humus content. The pH of soil was near neutral and slightly decreased by the depth. Water capacity of soil was low according to the soil type. The texture grade of soil was sandy according to the soil plasticity index (K_A) (Table 2).

Table 2

Results of soil analysis (Nyírbátor, 2012)

Parameters	Depth (cm)	
	0-30	30-60
pH (KCl)	7.47	6.38
Water soluble salts (%)	< 0.02	< 0.02
Plasticity index (K_A)	29	27
Humus content (%)	1.001	0.557
(NO_3+NO_2)-N (mg/kg)	9.12	4.61
P_2O_5 (mg/kg) (AL)	746	216
K_2O (mg/kg) (AL)	164	89.4
Mg (mg/kg)	80.5	66.2
Mn (mg/kg)	67.8	98.5
Cu (mg/kg)	4.586	1.594
Zn (mg/kg)	8.93	1.898

The soil organic matter content was low and decreased by the depth. The N-supply of the soil was medium, which was good correlation with the measured mineral N-forms. The mineral N fraction of the soil was dramatically decreased by the depth (Table 2).

Carbonate content of soil was not detectable. Available soil P (AL soluble) was high mostly in the upper layer of the soil. Available soil K content (AL soluble) was low and decreased by the depth. These results pointed out that the macronutrients were concentrated in the upper layer of the soil. Soil Mg and micronutrient contents were suitable for fruit growing (Table 2). The data on micronutrient contents correspond to the values characteristic to sandy soil with low humus content and pH value.

Leaf sampling and preparation

The leaves of the selected cultivar were used for plant sampling. Leaves were taken from twenty trees from the treatment plots at the standard sampling time (at the beginning of August). For sampling, healthy, well-developed, mature leaves (twenty leaves per replication) were taken from the mid-third portion of extension shoots of the current year as described in the international and Hungarian plant sampling guidelines for fruit orchards (Stiles, Reid, 1966; Hungarian standard MI-08 0468-81).

Fruit analysis

The concentration of flavonoids was measured by Kim et al. (2003), the total phenolic compounds were determined by Singleton and Rossi (1965) while the total water soluble antioxidant capacity (FRAP value) was evaluated according to Benzie and Strain (1996).

The soluble solid content of fruits (SSC) was measured by hand refractometer Brix (MT-032ATC, detection limit: $\pm 0.20\%$) (MSZ EN 12143:1998), the titratable acid content was measured by potentiometric titration according to Hungarian standard (MSZ ISO 750:2001). The dry matter content of fruits was determined by loss-ignition method. The ash content of fruits was determined according to Hungarian standard MSZ ISO 5520:1994. The vitamin C content was measured by iodine titration.

Statistical analysis

All the obtained data were tabulated and statistically analyzed according to Svab (1981) using the L.S.D. test at 5% level to recognize the significance of the differences between various treatment methods. The effects of the different treatments were assessed within ANOVA and Fisher's least significant differences were calculated following a significant ($P \leq 0.05$) F test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of leaf analysis

Results of leaf analysis were shown in the Table 3.

Foliar application of Wuxal and OGG significantly influenced the N content of apple leaves. The other treatments not affected significantly leaf N content (Table 3).

Table 3

Results of leaf analysis (Nyírbátor, 2012)

Treatments	N (%)	P (%)	K (%)	Ca (%)	Mg (%)
Control	2.24 a	0.177 b	1.34 b	1.84 a	0.377 a
Globalga	2.15 a	0.186 b	1.62 bc	1.96 b	0.356 a
Goemar BM 86	2.18 a	0.146 a	1.08 a	1.72 a	0.377 a
OGG	2.44 b	0.159 a	1.02 a	1.39 a	0.400 b
Wuxal Ascofol	2.39 b	0.163 a	1.00 a	1.50 a	0.391 a

In each column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$).

Leaf P, K and Ca were increased by the Globalga treatment only. Leaf P, K, and Ca content were lower when applying other treatments compared

to the control (Table 3). Leaf Mg was significantly affected and increased by the OGG treatment only.

Independently of the treatments the leaf macronutrient status was optimal for all examined nutrients. It was found that the leaf macronutrient status was not affected by the treatments consequently. This result is highly similar to the findings of Khan et al. (2012) who reported that foliar treated grapevines (mixture of amino acids and seaweed extract) showed no significant change in the leaf mineral contents.

Results of fruit analysis

Fruit samples were taken at the time of full ripening (31th August). The results of fruit analysis (external parameters) are shown in Table 4. Fruit size (diameter), mean weight and shape index were measured as external fruit parameters. Fruit diameters were measured at two time: at the middle of June and at the end of August (picking time).

Table 4

Results of fruit analysis (external parameters) (Nyírbátor, 2012)

Treatments	Fruit diameter (mm) (15.06.)	Fruit diameter (mm) (31.08.)	Mean weight* (g)	Shape index**
Control	32.86 a	60.98 a	101.75 a	0.86 a
Globalga	36.31 c	65.93 b	126.00 c	0.88 b
Wuxal Ascofol	35.73b c	66.99 b	128.75 c	0.85 a
Goemar BM 86	36.38 c	67.82 b	132.75 c	0.84 a
OGG	34.51 b	62.54 a	112.50 b	0.86 a

In each column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$).

*- mean weight of 100 fruits

** - ratio of height and width

All applied treatments significantly affected the fruit diameter, except OGG at the end of August. Goemar BM 86 resulted the highest increment in fruit diameter (11.2%). All treatments had significant positive effect on the weight of fruits. The Goemar BM 86 treatment resulted the highest mean weight. The increment was 30.5% compared to the control. These results are similar to those obtained from pear by Colavita et al., 2011.

Goemar BM 86 tends to have positive influence in acceleration of ripening and increase of fruit size. These results are in harmony with those obtained by Krok and Wieniarska 2008, who use of any biostimulator in primocane raspberry growing under conditions of Poland. that respect, its

effects are not consistent, however, varying depending on cultivar and or season.

The results of fruit analysis (internal parameters) are shown in Table 5, 6 and 7. Dry matter, ash and ascorbic acid content of fruits are showed in Table 5.

All applied biostimulator increased the fruit dry matter but only the Wuxal treatment resulted significant effect on it. Similar results were obtained regarding to the vitamin C content of fruits. Treatments had not significant effect on the ash content of fruits (Table 5).

Total sugar and acid content of fruits are shown in Table 6. All treatments increased the total sugar content of fruits, except OGG. But only the Goemar BM 86 treatment increased significantly the total sugar content of apples. However, the treatments had not significant effect on total acid content of apples. Total acid content of apples was varied between 1.1 and 1.4 g/l.

Table 5

Results of fruit analysis (internal parameters – I.) (Nyírbátor, 2012)

Treatments	Dry matter (%)	Ash (%)	Vitamin C (%)
Control	13.18 a	0.30 a	1.47 a
Globalga	13.43 a	0.29 a	1.47 a
Wuxal Ascofol	15.81 b	0.37 a	3.38 b
Goemar BM 86	14.53 a	0.33 a	2.35 a
Green Gold	14.18 a	0.35 a	2.05 a

In each column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$).

Table 6

Results of fruit analysis (internal parameters – II.) (Nyírbátor, 2012)

Treatments	Total sugar content (g/l)	Total acid content (g/l)
Control	108.30 a	1.20 a
Globalga	108.59 a	1.10 a
Wuxal Ascofol	109.59 a	1.40 a
Goemar BM 86	112.46 b	1.10 a
OGG	106.87 a	1.30 a

In each column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$).

Flavonoids, phenolic compounds and FRAP values of fruits are shown in Table 7. Flavonoid concentration in fruits varied between 0.187 and 0.346. The highest value was observed at the Wuxal treatment. Similarly to Wuxal, OGG had a strong, significant effect on the amount of flavonoids.

Table 7

Results of fruit analysis (internal parameters – III.) (Nyírbátor, 2012)

Treatments	Flavonoids (mg katechine ekv./100g fresh weight)	Phenolic compounds (mg gallic acid ekv./100g fresh weight)	FRAP (mg ascorbic acid ekv./100g fresh weight)
Control	0.196 a	47.593 a	34.604 a
Globalga	0.187 a	50.311 b	34.287 a
Wuxal Ascofol	0.346 b	69.234 c	55.250 c
Goemar BM 86	0.202 a	59.563 c	35.215 a
OGG	0.250 b	51.483 b	40.088 b

In each column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$).

Total phenolic content in fresh fruit samples was significantly affected by all applied treatments. It means, that the biostimulators increased the phenolic concentration in the apple samples. The Wuxal treatment was the most effective. The Wuxal treatment resulted the highest FRAP value similarly to those founded at flavonoids and phenolic compounds. It seems that among the treatments the Wuxal treatment had the strongest effect on measured so called “healthy protective” compounds. These results are in harmony with those obtained by Karim and Rahim, 2008 and Abd El-Motty et al., 2010 at Mango trees.

CONCLUSIONS

Our investigation was set up in a 14 years old apple orchard, planted on an acidic sandy soil, among unfavourable soil and climatic conditions. Four algae suspension as biostimulants were used in this comparing study.

Similarly, to the findings of Khan et al. (2012), it was found that the leaf macronutrient status was not affected by the treatments consequently and significantly. Furthermore, longer experiment is needed to study the effect of these products on leaf nutrient status.

Applied algae products and their doses significantly affected the fruit diameter and weight. It confirms the earlier findings that the PBs are useful to improve yield (Bulgari et al., 2014; Calvo et al., 2014; Yakhin et al., 2017).

Significant fruit diameter increment was observed in the early phenological stage, near after the foliar application.

All treatments increased the dry matter and the vitamin C content of apples compared to the control but significant effect was measured by using Wuxal Ascofol. Moreover, applied biostimulants had no significant effect on fruit ash and acid content. These results confirmed the earlier findings (Vernieri et al., 2005) that the efficacy of the biostimulants depends from the timing of application. Since biostimulants activate specific biochemical

mechanisms, it is important to identify the best application time. The optimal dose is also very important because within a certain range the crop can positively respond to biostimulants application. Therefore, it is important to define for each biostimulant the optimal application range, too high or low concentrations can nullify the biostimulant effect (Toscano et al., 2018; Vernieri et al., 2005).

Moreover, from these results it would be foolhardy to state that applying biostimulants in fruit growing provides greater health benefits than those produced without them, but we suggest that these comparison studies should be expanded. The real benefit of these studies is that they can identify and establish the production input weaknesses and strengths that affect nutrition, so that changes can be made to improve both organic and integrated fruit production technologies.

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